

Demo concepts & designs / D4.1

WP4, Task 4.1

Authors: Laura Reus Losa (SOO), Gerardo Wadel (SOO) and Jeroen Poppe (VUB)

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1. Technical references

Project Acronym	RECONSTRUCT
Project Title	A Territorial Construction System for a Circular, Low-Carbon Built Environment
GA number	101082265
Project Coordinator	Kathleen Blanco Instituto de Tecnología de la Construcción de Cataluña Head of Innovation Project Management Department kblanco@itec.cat
Project Duration	June 2023 – May 2027 (48 months)
Deliverable No.	D4.1
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 4 - Construction of circular demo buildings
Task	Task 4.1 Mission statement, concept, and design through co-creation
Lead beneficiary	10. SOO
Contributing beneficiary/ies	1. ITEC, 2. HOL, 3. CTC, 6. COM, 8. SOR, 9. VUB, 13. INC, 14. GEP,
Due date of deliverable	29 February 2024
Actual submission date	06 March 2024

* PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)

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V	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1.0	18/02/2024	First Draft (SOO, VUB)	Laura Reus Losa, Gerardo Wadel (SOO) Jeroen Poppe (VUB)
2.0	21/02/2024	First Review	Jacopo Donnini (UNIVPM)
3.0	27/02/2024	Second Review	Alexandros Chatzipavlidis (ICCS)
4.0	06/03/2024	Final Report (SOO, VUB)	Laura Reus Losa (SOO) Jeroen Poppe (VUB)

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3. Introduction

3.1. Demonstrating pathways to a net-zero future

The building sector in Europe, like in many other regions, has significant environmental impacts throughout its lifecycle. These impacts include resource extraction, energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, waste generation and habitat disruption. Globally, the Construction industry is responsible for over 30% of the extraction of natural resources, 25% of solid waste generated¹ and 40% of Greenhouse Gases (GHG) emissions². Around a third of these emissions come from embodied carbon in construction³ -the emissions created from the construction, demolition and the wider supply chain of a building.

To address these environmental impacts, the European Commission has been promoting sustainability in the building sector through various policies and initiatives. Those most closely related to the construction sector are:

- The European Green Deal⁴ outlines the European Commission's ambition to make the EU climate-neutral by 2050.
- The Renovation Wave Strategy aims to double the renovation rate of buildings by 2030, making buildings in the EU more energy-efficient and decarbonized.
- The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) establishes requirements for energy performance certificates and the promotion of nearly zero-energy buildings.
- The Circular Economy Action Plan promotes deconstruction, reuse and recycling, and minimizing construction and demolition waste extending the buildings' lifespan.
- The Sustainable Finance Strategy integrates environmental, social, and governance (ESG) considerations into the financial system by encouraging green investments.

¹ Gabriel Luiz Fritz Benachio, Maria do Carmo Duarte Freitas, Sergio Fernando Tavares, Circular economy in the construction industry: A systematic literature review, Journal of Cleaner Production, Volume 260, 2020, 121046, ISSN 0959-6526, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121046>

² European Commission, Level(s): [Level\(s\) - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/level-s/)

³ Bringing embodied carbon upfront, World Green Building Council, sep. 2019: https://worldgbc.s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/22123951/WorldGBC_Bringing_Embodied_Carbon_Upfront.pdf

⁴ The European Green Deal, European Commission: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

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- The EU taxonomy defines criteria for economic activities that are aligned with a net zero trajectory by 2050 and broader environmental goals other than climate.
- The Level(s) common language for assessing and reporting on the sustainability performance of buildings, applying circular economy principles in the built environment.
- The Horizon Europe research and innovation program focuses on achieving climate-neutral and smart cities, including buildings.

According to the European Commission (EC), greater material efficiency could save 80% of these emissions⁵, with cement and steel being the materials responsible for most of the embodied GHGs⁶. Cement and steel, components of reinforced concrete, which is the predominant structural material in many countries such as Spain, face different challenges in terms of material efficiency.

- For steel, recycling rates in Europe are already at 90%⁷, with construction steel approaching 100%. Using steel scrap in the production process does reduce CO₂ emissions by 58%, but there is no room for further improvement of recycling rates. Further GHG reduction through steel industry electrification and green energy will not start taking place before 2030.
- Cement, on the other hand, is almost exclusively used in concrete production. Although concrete is partially recyclable (e.g. as aggregate in new concrete) thus diverting CDW from the landfill, the cement contained therein is not recyclable. Therefore, concrete recycling does not reduce the demand/consumption of cement and results in a marginal reduction of concrete's carbon footprint (>80% of which is owed to cement). With recycling of cement and steel having limited potential for improving material efficiency and achieving the industry's targets, the focus is on replacing steel and cement with low-carbon alternatives and/or reducing the amounts of cement and steel used by embedding them in durable, repairable and reusable construction components. Finally, established CDW material loops must expand to include other waste.

Following these guidelines, the Reconstruct project will develop:

- Low-carbon alternatives to OPC by incorporating CDW and other waste as much as possible.

⁵ A new Circular Economy Action Plan, Brussels, 11.3.2020, COM(2020) 98 final; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0098>

⁶ United Nations Environment Programme, & Yale Center for Ecosystems + Architecture (2023). Building Materials and the Climate: Constructing a New Future. <https://wedocs.unep.org/20.500.11822/43293>.

⁷ <https://metinvestholding.com/en/media/news/stalij-kak-samij-pererabativaemij-material-v-mire>

- Manufacture construction components that use such materials and are designed for modularity and dismantling so they can either be reused/ repaired or easily disassembled and recycled.
- Embed deconstruction and multifunctionality considerations in building design and construct circular low-carbon buildings that produce near-zero CDW across their lifecycle.
- Completely modular and prefabricated construction approach for one of the demos.

These objectives will become possible through the digitization to test the Reconstruct digital workflow and monitor the materials impacts assessment, both at the product and building level. Also, regionalization of the construction value chain through the creation of regional ecosystems of stakeholders covering all the aspects of circular construction will be a focus of the demos.

The Reconstruct concept will be validated by designing and building two real-scale demonstrator buildings, using Reconstruct's materials, components and innovative digital tools to design and construct. These demos are the central content of this document. By doing so, Reconstruct aims to demonstrate its high impact potential in terms of reducing GHG emissions, resource use, and waste generation and its economic feasibility, showing different pathways to a net-zero future for concrete by 2050.

In the first chapter of the report, the differences between the demos and an overview of the experiments that will be carried out to achieve Reconstruct's objectives are described. In the second and third chapters, each demo is explained in detail, followed by the next steps to be taken and ending in chapter four with the conclusions at this stage of the project and the future ambitions of both demos.

4. Demo Concept and Experiments

4.1. Two demos, two settings

During the four years of the Reconstruct project, from June 2023 to May 2027, the purpose of the Reconstruct project is to work with the sector to develop new **concrete compositions and components** that are both **low-carbon** and **designed for disassembly**, improving substantially on conventional construction practices in terms of **GHG emissions, resource use, and waste generation** on-site and at the end of the life cycle. The ultimate goal is to provide circular solutions throughout the entire life cycle of a building to enable a circular future for concrete.

The **feasibility** and **viability** of these new solutions will be demonstrated in **two demonstration projects**, one in Brussels and one in Barcelona, representing different building contexts and use cases. Both buildings will be digitised to test the Reconstruct **digital workflow**, and they will be monitored to assess **material impacts** both at the product and building level. As such, the pilots will show different pathways to **a net-zero future for concrete** by 2050

Figure 1. Location of the two demos

Therefore, **two real-scale** demo buildings will be built in two locations, Barcelona and Brussels, both representing urban contexts but each with a distinct construction philosophy. The two regions also offer contrasting settings: they have different **climatic conditions, building traditions, value chains** and, they are at different positions on the **transition curve to zero carbon**. Local building codes, norms and standards further differentiate the design of the two pilots. Apart from the differences in context, the two demo projects are also designed to be complementary in **typology** and **construction methods**. While the Barcelona demo aims to validate solutions representative for **multi-family residential construction**, the building system implemented in the Brussels demo is specifically designed for **tertiary buildings**.

Both **traditional, onsite construction** methods (the dominant approach in Europe) and **modular, offsite construction** methods (an approach that is increasingly gaining ground and adopted in North and Central Europe) will be represented in the demos in order to explore and compare their potential for circularity. Recognising that in Europe, **circular renovation and reconversion strategies** will be central in decarbonising the building stock¹, particular attention will be given to the reusability or recyclability of deconstructed materials/components during the Reconstruct project in partners' commercial projects involving renovation, or ultimately, in other second-hand marketplaces or industries.

Demo	Spanish demo	Belgian demo
Building site	Castle grounds of Santa Perpètua de Moguda, Barcelona	Green Energy Park, Zellik, Brussels
Land management	Incasòl	Green Energy Park vzw
Construction method	On-site and off-site	Off-site
Net Floor Area	Approx. 50 m ²	Approx. 50 m ²
Floors	1	2
Use	None (auxiliary building)	Office space
Usage requirements considered for replicability	Housing	Office
Components to be tested	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foundation slab • Vertical structure • Facade panels • Exterior pavement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prefab sandwich elements with TRC shells (phase 1) • Prefab sandwich elements with TRC shells and circular concrete core (phase 2)
Elements to be disassembled and reconstructed	Facade panels and substructure	Sandwich panel of the storey floor

Table 1: Characteristics of each demo

Figure 2. Brussels demo –Holland Composites

Figure 3. Barcelona demo – Societat Orgànica

4.2. Experiments and Objectives

As explained, a full cycle of design, construction, (partial) renovation, deconstruction and reuse/recycling will be completed across the demos to demonstrate the circularity potential, mainly in solutions of concrete, and the sustainability impact of the concept in different contexts. This will be approached from three complementary perspectives: **material innovation, design for deconstruction and digitalisation**. These three strategies encompass the different experiments to be carried out in each demo in order to achieve the final objectives. They are explained in the following table:

	Barcelona	Brussels
Urban context Level	<p>Digitalization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-based technology for CDW quantification and characterisation to feed into SYNER platform • Tool of Symbiosis potential • Reincorporate the deconstructed materials in marketplaces for reclaimed materials or building sites • Reintroduce the demolished materials in the recycling loop 	<p>Digitalization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reincorporate the deconstructed materials in other building sites of the material producer-construction company

<p>Building Level</p>	<p>Digitalization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking and tracing with digital twinning in BIM • Collection of real-life data from demo (training of the AI models) • LCC, LCA, Circular Assessment methodology & data <p>Design for deconstruction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partial dismantling and change of the space configuration of some parts of the building, rebuilding these parts – Test assemble - disassemble – maintain/reuse • Adaptability • Generate minimum waste on-site 	<p>Digitalization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking and tracing with digital twinning in BIM • LCC, LCA, Circular Assessment methodology & data <p>Design for deconstruction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partial dismantling & replacement with new components from newly developed materials of some parts of the building – Test assemble – disassemble – replacement. • Adaptability • Generate minimum waste on-site
<p>Product/ Material Level</p>	<p>Digitalization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking and tracing with Product passports in BIM • LCC, LCA, Circular Assessment data & dataflow with PP <p>Material Innovation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Replace ordinary Portland cement with low-carbon alternatives, either recycled or bio-based • Replace coarse aggregates in concrete with recycled aggregates • Replace steel reinforcement with textile reinforcement <p>Design for deconstruction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reversible joint components easy to disassemble by parts or pieces • facilitate the separation of materials within the same product to enable recycling 	<p>Digitalization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracking and tracing with Product passports in BIM • LCC, LCA, Circular Assessment data & dataflow with PP <p>Material Innovation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Replace ordinary Portland cement with low-carbon alternatives, either recycled or bio-based • Replace steel reinforcement with textile reinforcement <p>Design for deconstruction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • building structures as a kit of parts, made of modular, prefabricated components that are easy to assemble and disassemble and reuse

Table 2: Planned experiments for each demo

As can be shown, some experiments implemented will be common to both demos such as the replacement of ordinary Portland cement with low-carbon alternatives, either recycled or bio-based, and the steel reinforcement with textile reinforcement, the easiness to disassemble components, the partial dismantling, the intention of generate minimum waste and reuse de deconstructed material in other building sites or the tracking and tracing with digital twinning in BIM and the impact evaluation through circular assessments. Other experiments will be unique due to the regional context, use and objective of each one like the incorporation of recycled coarse aggregates in the cast-in-place concrete for the Barcelona demo.

The different phases to develop these demos will involve 16 partners from across the continent, mainly in Spain, Belgium and the Netherlands, from industry, government and research. They will be working with stakeholders in two regional clusters settled up in Barcelona and Brussels validating the experiments and results, creating synergies and promoting future applications, among other actions. The characteristics, phases, plan and experiments of each prototype are explained in detail below, [3. Barcelona demo. Design & Concepts](#) and [4. Brussels demo. Design & Concepts](#).

4.3. Planning and KPIs

Below is a summarized timeline representation of the planning for both demos.

Figure 4. Demo's Timeline

Going into further detail, the project will proceed through the following distinct phases:

Design and planning: *June 2023 – June 2024*

- Project brief and description
- Design of the demos: characteristics, plans, timeline, experiments, roles & budgets through co-creation sessions
- List of permits and requirements
- Scouting material sources
- Setting KPIs for impact assessment

Development (Materials and Dataflow): *December 2023 – May 2026*

- Testing materials and components
- Digital material sourcing, definition of product passports, digital twin functions & BIM

Demonstration: *June 2024 – March 2027*

- Request for permits (depending on the demo)
- Construction: Belgium demo – *starting September 2024* & Barcelona demo – *starting November 2025*
- Partial dismantling & replacement with new components from newly developed materials in Brussels demo – *starting June 2025*

- Partial dismantling & reconstruction to change the space configuration in Barcelona demo – *starting May 2026*
- Deconstruction: Barcelona demo – *starting December 2026*

Assessment: *November 2025 – May 2027*

- Monitor and assess the environmental assessment of the demos
- Reuse options for the old elements in other (commercial) projects or incorporation into marketplaces
- Recycling options and routes for CDW

Validation & Replication: *March 2024 – May 2027*

- Collect lessons learnt on all topics > Create framework + Info packs for replication
- Commercial feasibility study and search for investors or interested parties – *starting May 2026*
- Stakeholder training & dissemination

Finally, to evaluate and monitor the final objectives pursued in these local demonstrations, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined and considered during the development of the design of the prototypes and materials incorporated. These KPIs will be reviewed and monitored during the remaining phases of the project and, ultimately, updated if they are not achieved.

- Virgin content in building: 50%
- Reusable and/or recyclable content: 80%
- Locally available content: 100%
- Waste intensity during construction: 0%
- Material-to-surface ratio: better/equal than comparable buildings

In this context, the local available concept will refer to a regional scale, generally covering the territory of the autonomous region. Regarding the material-to-surface ratio, the conventional ratio will have to be defined as a basis for comparing the final result, analysing reliable statistical sources for each region where the demo is located and for each type of use. Finally, specify that waste intensity in this case is understood as a reduction of construction waste sent to landfill, since a minimum amount of waste will be generated, such as packaging, cut pieces or discards or waste from the on-site construction of the Barcelona demo, but these will be sent for recycling and/or reused in other works, reducing landfill to zero.

4.4. Barcelona

The Spanish demo will be located in an exterior area within the enclosure of Mogoda's Castle, situated in Santa Perpetua de la Moguda (part of Barcelona Metropolitan Area), property of project partner Incasòl. Incasòl is a body of the Generalitat de Catalunya which depends on the Department of Territory and Sustainability and is mainly in charge of the promotion of public residential land. Particularly, in this location, Incasòl has just recently completed the execution of a project for converting the castle to a polyvalent centre for conferences, research, innovation, and education. Surrounding the castle there is ample land where to build the demonstrator, specifically at the rear of the castle which is not a regular public access area or part of the castle tours, serving for internal events organized by Incasòl.

During the project the consortium will be able to use this space and demo to organise open labs or demonstratives trainings in situ once the building is constructed but, the uses of holding meetings, conferences, expositions and other dissemination activities, will finally be moved to the space renovated by Incasòl inside the Santa Perpetua Castle which has all the possible facilities to accommodate these events like bathrooms, coffee room, equipment for conferences, lighting and acclimatized spaces. This is due to the fact that the Santa Perpetua Castle site is an urban special protected area^{8 9} that allows only temporary works and thus, the demo will have to be dismantled at the end of the project, a novelty compared to what was initially proposed, where the idea was a multipurpose demonstrator that would later become an Information Point on the evolution of Mogoda's Castle and/or a centre for showcasing and educating on circular construction practices at the project's completion. The construction allowed by regulation on this land includes uses of "temporary uses and works" or "storage, porches and auxiliary buildings"¹⁰, as corroborated by the Municipality. Other uses and activities that will be implemented within the project, except for open labs in the demos, will be relegated to the refurbishment of the interior of the castle as mentioned above.

⁸ Pla General Municipal d'Ordenació de Santa Perpetua de la Moguda - Text refós de les Normes urbanístiques del planejament general, aprovat 1996 i 2005: <https://dtes.gencat.cat/rpucportal/#/consulta/detallExpedient/221024/documents>

⁹ Pla especial de Protecció del Patrimoni Arquitectònic de Santa Perpetua de la Moguda, Nov 1996: <https://dtes.gencat.cat/rpucportal/#/consulta/detallExpedient/89195/documents>

¹⁰ Ordenança reguladora dels procediments d'intervenció administrativa municipal sobre l'ús del sòl i edificació: llicències urbanístiques i comunicacions prèvies: [BOP- DIBA](#)

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Figure 5. Sta Perpetua's Castle, location of the Barcelona demo

Although the demo will be built as a temporary auxiliary building, it will be designed taking into account compliance with housing regulations in a theoretical way, with the intention that this prototype could be replicable for residential use. This means that when applying for the building permit for this type of building, is not mandatory to comply, for example, with part of the regulations of the Spanish Technical Code (CTE) such as the Basic Document on Energy Saving (DB-HE)¹¹ but solutions will be designed considering that they could accommodate the necessary amount of insulation to meet the minimum transmittance for residential use in Barcelona's climate or for the passage of the necessary facilities, although they are not mandatory and will not be incorporated in the demonstration. The residential use is proposed since the most common building use built in Spain statistically in 2021¹² were 3 to 5-storey residential blocks, choosing this most representative and replicable type of building to focus the proposed solutions. At the same time, it will serve to test a different use from the Belgian demonstrative (office). Incasòl will take on the role of the promoter in this building as well as the client. As it is a public body, it will help in the wider dissemination.

The demo will consist of a one-story modular building with a rectangular floor plan of 46,55 m². A foundation slab will be cast in place, as conventionally in situ solutions of concrete, but with AAC cement and recycled aggregates. The vertical structure will be constituted by eight pillars of 0.25 x 0.25 m, also cast on site with a similar concrete mix. The façades will be closed with easy-to-disassemble precast concrete panels floor to roof high of AAC-based concrete reinforced with biobased composite bars instead of steel. The combination of these two materials will guarantee higher durability than with conventional steel bars and will lengthen the lifespan of the panels. In the surroundings of the building, 75 m² of

¹¹ CTE- DB HE (in spanish): <https://www.codigotecnico.org/DocumentosCTE/AhorroEnergia.html>

¹² Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE)
<https://ine.es/Censo2021/Wizard.do?WIZARD=5&reqCode=pasoSeleccionColectivo>

removable AAC-based paving blocks with also recycled aggregates will be placed to complete the demonstrator.

Finally, for the roof, a light conventional or textile solution, also easy to disassemble, will be installed, supported by a light structure. The idea is to source and reuse this type of roofing from other COMSA construction sites or tensioned textile roofs from ephemeral events that are economically viable in the project. The demonstrator will be built in one single phase once the materials and components developed in the project are finalised and the external products are supplied by the providers, different from the Brussels demo.

A change of surface, recessing the building envelope will be demonstrated with the prefabricated façade panels, and the reuse of these elements together with the paving stones and roofing in other constructions when the building is completely deconstructed will also be evaluated. The choice of easy-to-disassemble precast components together with the use of ACC with a high content of recycled by-products and recycled coarse aggregates in concrete mass will demonstrate the possibility of construction contributing to the circular economy from the sector of concrete.

4.5. Brussels

The Belgian demo building will be constructed on the premises of partner Green Energy Park (GEP), located in Zellik (Brussels) near the Brussels airport and the University of Brussels (VUB) in a green scenery. GEP is a living lab where testing and optimization of innovations can be done in a realistic environment, founded in 2019 by VUB and the University Hospital. The demonstrative will house a **shared office** space that will be used by Green Energy Park members for their administrative activities, meetings and events and will thereby comply with the relevant national and local legislation regarding office use. Once built, despite being a private use, it will be able to host open labs, training or hold meetings for the proper development of Reconstruct and to increase the dissemination of the circular construction.

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Figure 6. Green Energy Research Park, location of the Brussels demo – Source: GEP

As it is an office building, different aspects will be explored from those tested in the Barcelona demo, which is designed for residential use. Green Energy Park will be the client and end-user of this building. Given its affiliation with the University as a Research Park, promotion and dissemination within the academic community are ensured.

The demo will consist of a modular office building with a rectangular floor plan of 63 m² distributed over two floors. It will follow the **prefab approach to construction** with all its elements manufactured off-site but assembled on light foundations onsite, facilitating the future disassembly/reassembly. The system uses a hybrid structure, combining a steel framework with lightweight sandwich elements for the facades, floors and roof, made of bio-resin shells and recycled, PET-foam cores. This system, branded as Qbix, is based on a commercial one already developed by Holland Composites, a Dutch company dedicated to the manufacture of bio-based composites that offers advanced composite structures in the form of modular kits to be directly assembled on-site, creating modular buildings, generally one-story office or housing buildings.

The Qbix system was designed specifically for the healthcare sector, and it works well for **single-storey buildings**. In the years to come, Holland Composites wants to expand the system to **multi-storey applications**. In that case, the storey floors will have to meet higher requirements in terms of **load capacity, fire resistance and acoustic insulation**, making concrete the more obvious material choice over lightweight PET foam. Based on the use case of Holland Composites, it will be developed a **new, concrete sandwich element**, that goes beyond current practices in the sector. Combining **textile-reinforced concrete shells** and an **alkali-activated concrete core**, to goal of the demo partners is to drastically minimise **material use** and **GHG emissions** of the component, to assess its **feasibility** and **viability** as a commercial solution and bring it to the market.

To test the new concept for the storey floors the demo will be constructed in two phases. In the first phase, the storey floor elements used, will be combining the existing PET foam cores with new, TRC shells developed by VUB, instead of the bio-resin composites. In the

second phase, at least one of the storey floor elements will be replaced with a new one¹³, combining TRC shells with a lightweight AAC concrete core. These new components will be evaluated in terms of their **environmental impact**, the **spatial adaptability** they allow in creating flexible plan layouts, and the potential they have for **deconstruction and reuse**. The choice of modular prefabricated components that are easy to disassemble and are durable together with the aim of reaching 100 % secondary resource materials for use in a mortar for TRC production, foam for the core, and concrete for foundation will demonstrate the possibility for construction to contribute to the circular economy from the prefabricated kits sector. Also, recyclability would be considered in this TRC sandwich panels.

¹³ The largest challenge lies exactly in designing floor systems removable, while ensuring the load bearing capacity for an intermediate floor, the acoustical requirements, the fire requirements and the extra complication arising from the use of technical floors in offices. This element will be the most innovative for the built prototype, together with the conceptual design of modular prefabrication that enables real adaptability.

5. Barcelona demo. Design & concept.

This chapter defines the sections, specifications and regulations required to justify projects of this type of *auxiliary buildings* (temporal, non-habitable) in Santa Perpetua. The elaboration of the technical project is necessary to obtain the building permits from the Municipality and to carry out the corresponding construction works. It has been similarly structured to the drafting of an executive project (not the graphic documentation) to facilitate and speed up its future redaction by the Architect in June 2025. We have also added sections outside the content of technical projects to clarify questions about the development and conception of the *Reconstruct* project, such as the challenges faced during the co-creation and design sessions and the future steps to be followed for the construction of the demo.

5.1. Actors, roles and responsibilities

The actors involved in the development of the “DEMONSTRATIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PROJECT RECONSTRUCT IN BARCELONA” are defined according to their roles in the table below.

Financial Developer	Under the funding of the European Research Executive Agency (REA) through the Project: 101082265 — RECONSTRUCT — HORIZON-CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-02-two-stage. Derived via consortium partners.
Building owner	INCASOL C/ de Còrsega, 273 08008, Barcelona
Designer and Construction Manager	Architect: to be defined Registration number: XXXX Architect Body: COAC
Execution Manager (construction & deconstruction)	COMSA SAU C/ Viriato, 47 08014, Barcelona.
Consultors for co-design	<u>Research sector</u> : Societat Orgànica +10 SCCL, Instituto de Tecnología de la Construcción (ITEC, Catalunya), Simbiosi Industrial S.L. <u>Industrial sector</u> : COMSA Corporación, Sorigué, Centro Tecnológico de la Construcción Región de Murcia (CTCON). <u>Government institution</u> : Institut Català el Sòl (INCASOL).

Table 3: Actors involved in the development of the Barcelona demo

In addition, internal roles not specified above, in the development of the Barcelona demo are defined below.

The management and budgeting necessary for the building permits fees	INCASOL
Geotechnical assessments report	Subcontracted by project partners
Materials development	Centro Tecnológico de la Construcción Región de Murcia (CTCON), Università Politecnica delle Marche (UNIVPM)
Components development	Sorigué
Purchase of materials/components not developed inside the consortium	Anchors/ substructure for panels - Suppliers from outside the consortium
Recovery/reuse routes to divert CDW and produced surpluses	Simbiosi Industrial S.L., Societat Orgànica +10 SCCL
BIM model implementer	Societat Orgànica +10 SCCL
Circularity (and adaptability) analysis	Societat Orgànica +10 SCCL

Table 4: Other actors involved in the development of the Barcelona demo.

5.2. Design Process

The design of the prototypes has been carried out through co-creation and validation sessions with partners inside the consortium and, especially, the design of the removable unions for the façade panels, with experts' collaborators and providers externs of the consortium. During these co-creation sessions, literature and actual commercial solutions in the market have been reviewed to design the most replicable solutions and to respond to the commercial needs of the internal partners.

The frequency of the sessions has been the following:

- Biweekly meeting between Societat Orgànica (Barcelona leader) and University of Brussels (Brussels leader) to update the vision/problems encountered and to coordinate the Barcelona and Brussels demos.
- Monthly meeting with Spanish planners (INCASOL, COMSA and Societat Orgànica) to define the location, permits needed for the construction and the legal requirements associated
- Two meetings between INCASOL, Societat Orgànica, ITEC and the Municipal Architect of Sta Perpetua Moguda to validate the permits needed for the construction and the legal & regulations requirements associated with the use of the demo
- One visit to the Barcelona location with INCASOL (developer and client), COMSA (constructor) and Societat Orgànica (coordinator and designer) to analyse possible locations for the building and define the final placement considering accessibility, ease of construction, visibility, construction safety, location of project-related activities

- Weekly meeting with Spanish planners and material/components developers (CTCON, Sorigué, COMSA, ITEC and Societat Orgànica) to define materials requirements and design the demo (plans, constructive elements and components characteristics, most replication/commercial solutions, improvement of conventional buildings and KPIs achievement)
- Two meetings with expert and engineer collaborators (external) to co-design dismountable unions for façade panels depending on the goals to achieve and develop its mechanical analysis/performance
- Three meetings with providers of steel connections (Hilti, Entinema, Tulipps Solar System solutions) to review the actual commercial solutions that can be removable per element and possible providers
- Once the concept and design of the Barcelona demo have been developed, and once a group of external stakeholders from different professions has been formed, it is intended to validate this collaborative design with them in order to find the needs and interests covered by each agent involved in the value chain and its future replicability. This session is intended to be documented but is scheduled for after the present report.

For the correct operation of these collaborative sessions, documents have been developed to support decision-making, where the problems to be solved and the progression of their resolution according to the agreements reached at the meetings, as well as the way to solve them, are set out. This document, in the case of the meetings between the Spanish planners and material/components developers, is summarized in Annex II. During these sessions, the following aspects were mainly agreed upon:

- Suitable use identified to justify the regulations in the Executive/ Technical Project for processing the necessary permits with the Municipal Council.
- Replicable use to be achieved, considering in a theoretical manner the mandatory regulations to be complied with for the design and justification of the construction solutions developed.
- The hypothesis of deconstruction and its planning within the timeframe of the project.
- Area, height and geometric definition of the building.
- Location of the building considering the context and ease of access by the equipment required for construction.
- Necessary permits and associated justification documents for the construction process
- Roles of each partner and the need for external partners
- Characteristics of each element considering the KPIs at the building level
- Experiments desired in each element both for the fulfilment of the KPIs and for the search for innovation and improvement regarding conventional solutions.
- Design of the constructive solutions with emphasis on their potential for deconstruction
- Necessary suppliers to obtain elements not included in the project.
- Replicability of the building as well as the possible future commercialization of the developed elements.

- Future of the materials of the building once deconstructed and routes for the valorization of construction waste (if needed).

In the following sections, we proceed to the description of the resulting design of the demo after these validation sessions. Some of these aspects have been left under development in view of the development of the Technical Project, planned from January 2025 to June 2025 to be able to be submitted in October 2025 maximum. The average time for issuance is between one and six months. The aspects that are in the process of final definition are:

- Final design of the removable unions (substructure, anchors) of the façade panels to the structure
- The constructive solutions details, depending on the final design of the connections
- Final suppliers that will provide the unions of the façade panels and light roofing/ pergola
- Construction Budget and measurements
- Justification of compliance with national and local regulations for the Executive Project
- Final destiny of Construction and Demolition “Waste” (components), developed from December 2024

5.3. Description of the demo

5.3.1. Background and initial conditioning factors

Once the project was started, we proceeded to the inspection of the site where the interventions defined in this report are to be carried out in order to choose the best location in the surroundings of the castle of Santa Perpetua according to the initial constraints. The rest of the information necessary for the drafting of the project (geometry, dimensions, surface of the plot of land owned and urban information), has been provided by the developer and is incorporated in this report.

The fundamental conditions taken into account in the selection of the site and consequently conditions of the building were as follows:

- Security of the site during construction (enclosed area, no need to hire extra security other than security for the castle facilities).
- Possibility of a water connection point nearby for the production of concrete and other processes related to the construction works.
- Possibility of nearby electricity connection for the construction works
- Ease of transport access to the construction site: accessible plot, avoidance of earthworks to create the access, avoidance of disturbance to neighbours along the transport routes.

- Avoid unnecessary felling of existing trees, and take advantage to create shaded outdoor space next to the building.
- Sufficient space and manoeuvrability for the handling of machinery such as cranes for heavy panels.
- Visibility and accessibility from the public part of the castle for the visit of the finished building.
- Greater separation from the train tracks, which transports hazardous substances.
- Lower probability of affecting the soil, as it is a protected land with the need of an archaeologist according to the use to be built.
- Aesthetic impact on neighbouring buildings.

Initially, three possible sites were proposed for the construction of the demo. After the site visit, it was detected that the location outside the Castle complex was not feasible due to the need to hire security guards for the security of the building during its construction and after, as it would be an open construction. Also due to the remoteness of the facilities refurbished by Incasòl where the main activities would take place during the visit to the demo. An advantage was a location that would not inconvenience the neighbours as the truck routes and the site were away from residential areas.

Figure 7. Sta Perpetua's Castle complex and the three possible locations for the demo

Of the two other sites within the enclosure, shown in the photographs and plans below, the final decision was for the site closest to the northwest private entrance, at the top of the plot. This site allows direct and easy access for construction trucks without the need for earth moving or crossing the interior of the site. In addition, it has a water connection on the same platform, the electrical installations of the other site allow the connection of electricity and is

in a less demanding regulatory area of the law of hazardous goods transportation by train¹⁴. Finally, it has better visibility from the public pedestrian access from the castle and it is the platform located on the highest slope of the plot, having less possibility of archaeological impact due to protected land.

Figure 8. Sta Perpetua's Castle complex location in Sta Perpetua de la Moguda

Figure 9. Final site of the demo inside Sta Perpetua's Castle complex, next to the restricted acces.

¹⁴ [Resolució INT/2330/2013](#)

Figure 10. View from the site of the demo, inside the complex, residential building can be seen.

Figure 11. Other possible location (site 3) for the demo inside Sta Perpetua's Castle complex, in the third platform.

The conditioning factors that have affected the conception of this project and that have been taken into account are as follows:

- **The definition of the use and project needs.** As it is a special protected area regarding the General Municipal Development Plan of Santa Perpetua de la Moguda of 1996 and the corresponding 2005 amended text¹⁵, only "temporary uses and works" buildings (Code 40) or "warehouse, porches and auxiliary buildings" (Code 53)¹⁶ could be built in this land qualification, being necessary its deconstruction at the end of the permitted activity. The uses in these urban planning regulations are restricted of the previous codes. This demo is not intended to house a specific use, but to be an open space (without an airtight roof, only a light element of protection from the rain/sun), a testing ground for the constructive elements we want to demonstrate: in situ structure, removable dry paving and facades. What we can call a temporary demonstrative pilot or installation. For this reason, we have identified the better compatible use in regulation would be "auxiliary buildings" (code 53), which is most in line with our definition. In addition, this choice allows us to reduce the number of supporting documents to be developed for the building permit application (see section [5.5 Obligatory regulations & implications](#)), allowing us to focus on internal documentation for the replicability of the demo in other uses.
- **Regulations.** Derived from the use, the works considered "auxiliary buildings" (in this locality regulated under Codi 53 of the Municipal Ordinance Regulating the use of land and buildings) and derived from their nature, those considered "minor works", are exempt from compliance with the Technical Building Code (CTE) and other local regulations. Except for the Basic Document on Structural Safety¹⁷ (DB SE) and waste management under the national law in vigour, that will be justified. Another of the administrative requirements to be verified for the urban development permit, are those derived from *Pla especial de protecció del patrimoni arquitectònic de Santa Perpetua de Mogoda (1996)*¹⁸, which specifies the "Location of the heritage listed in the PEPPASPM, areas of archaeological expectation and archaeological group", qualifying this site as a protected area but not an area of archaeological expectation.
- **Typological.** Although the built demo does not house a use, the design of the constructive solutions has been focused on being replicable in, mainly housing use, since the most common building type according to Spanish statistics from Instituto

¹⁵ [Pla General Municipal d'Ordenació de Santa Perpetua de la Moguda - Text refós de les Normes urbanístiques del planejament general \(1996 i 2005\)](#)

¹⁶ Ordenança reguladora dels procediments d'intervenció administrativa municipal sobre l'ús del sòl i edificació: llicències urbanístiques i comunicacions prèvies: [BOP- DIBA](#)

¹⁷ *Documento Básico de Seguridad Estructural* (DB SE) documentation (only Spanish language): <https://www.codigotecnico.org/DocumentosCTE/SeguridadEstructural.html>

¹⁸ <https://www.staperpetua.cat/ajuntament/normativa/urbanisme/planols/planol-darees-dexpectativa-arqueologica-i-paleontologica.html>

Nacional de Estadística (INE) up to 2021¹⁹ is housing blocks of 3 to 5 floors. In the design of the floor slab, the structural dimensions, the dimensions of the panels and the most common solutions used in housing buildings with concrete panels will be taken into account, always ensuring a substantial sustainable improvement over conventional solutions.

- **Environmental sustainability.** The planned interventions respond to the sustainability requirements of the Horizon Europe Reconstruct Project and aim to improve conventional concrete constructions. The intention is to achieve a reduction in the impact of CO₂ emissions, an increase in the amount of recycling of materials, an increase in material efficiency and a reduction of waste to a minimum. In addition, the use of local materials is encouraged. These requirements are defined in the KPIs, explained in section [2.3 Planning and KPIs](#).
- **Economic.** Within the possibilities of the project budget, we have eliminated the constructive solutions that are not intended to test or demonstrate the ultimate objectives of the project; together with the elements derived from compliance with the CTE DB HS, HR or HE, from which we are exempt (watertight joints, insulation, etc.). The economic effort will be focused on making it possible for the elements developed and built to be circular.

5.3.2. Location, environment and urban planning regulations

Location. The plot object of the demo is plot 1 of polygon 4 of La Mogoda from *Text refós de les Normes urbanístiques del planejament general*²⁰ of Santa Perpetua de la Moguda, belonging to Incasol's public land and located within the enclosure of the Moguda castle of Santa Perpetua de la Moguda. Its shape is polygonal, its perimeter is 186,5 x 300 x 231 x 164 m on each of its sides approximately and has a total floor area of 35.307 m². This plot includes all the enclosure, buildings and gardens of the Moguda Castle. The demo is located in the high and northwest area of the plot, a platform with a rectangular shape of 1.390 m² and with sides of dimensions 92,5 m on the longest side and 66,2 m on the shortest side of the rectangle. The slope is about 1 m at the most unfavourable point. The construction area of the demo is located at the back of the castle, which is not accessible to the public and is dedicated to the maintenance and internal management of the complex.

The final location can be seen in the figure 12 and figure 13.

¹⁹ <https://ine.es/Censo2021/Wizard.do?WIZARD=5&reqCode=pasoSeleccionColectivo>

²⁰ <https://dtes.gencat.cat/rpucportal/#/consulta/detallExpedient/221024/documents>

Figure 12. Final location for the demo inside Sta Perpetua's Castle complex.

Context. The complex of the Moguda Castle is located in the neighbourhood of La Moguda, a residential area of single-family houses in the suburbs of the city centre of Santa Perpetua, surrounded by vegetation or non-urbanized areas. The plot is bordered to the northeast by a pedestrian path in a vegetable area, unnamed to date, to the northwest and southeast by the public housing of the Moguda neighbourhood, and to the southwest by the railroad tracks of the freight line that connects the Santa Perpetua station with Martorell and Granollers Centre. The area where the demo is being built is located to the north of the parent plot where there is a small mass of vegetation and is bordered to the southwest by the back of the Moguda Castle and to the southeast by the rest of the land behind the castle without access to the public, unbuilt and free space with vegetation. The parent plot is located in the suburbs of the main urban centre of Santa Perpetua and to the southeast of it.

Vehicle access (and pedestrian access for construction personnel) will be via the Carrer Mogoda road that bounds the subsidized public housing in the Moguda neighbourhood to the northeast of the sector, close to the demo construction area. Pedestrian access for public visits to the demo will be from the main public entrance to the enclosure and Moguda Castle, to the northwest of the plot along the Carrer Mogoda road. Once inside the castle enclosure, the pedestrian walkway inside the castle will be traversed, exiting directly to the back of the castle, where the demo is located in a straight line from this rear access.

Figure 13. Sta Perpetua’s Castle complex location in Sta Perpetua de la Moguda

Urban planning regulations and other norms. The urban development regulations of the *Normes urbanístiques del planejament general*²¹ of Santa Perpetua de la Moguda.

- Allowed uses: Regarding *Codi 53* under the assumption "Warehouses, porches and auxiliary constructions (one-storey, with a volume of less than 75 m3, of a single crugia and not being of a residential or public character)".

Table 5: Regulatory framework for the Barcelona demo

Regulatory framework	Required	Recom.
<i>Código Técnico de la Edificación (CTE)</i> – Building Code		X
<i>Normes urbanístiques del planejament general de Santa Perpètua</i> – Local urban planning regulations ²⁰	X	
<i>Programa general de prevenció i gestió de residus i recursos de Catalunya (PRECAT20)</i> ²² – waste management	X	
<i>Pla especial de protecció del patrimoni arquitectònic de Santa Perpètua de Mogoda</i> ²³ - Heritage protection plan	X	

²¹ <https://dtes.gencat.cat/rpucportal/#/consulta/detallExpedient/221024/documents>

²² https://residus.gencat.cat/ca/ambits_dactuacio/planificacio/

²³ <https://dtes.gencat.cat/rpucportal/#/consulta/detallExpedient/89195/documents>

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5.3.3. General description of the development, program of requirements, characteristic use of the building and other intended uses, relationship with the surroundings.

General description of the development. This demo is not intended to house a specific use, but to be a testing ground for the constructive elements we want to demonstrate: in situ structure, removable dry paving and facades. It would be a temporary demonstrative pilot or installation, an open space without an airtight roof, only a light element of protection from the rain/sun but close by a facade of concrete panels, without doors or windows. The demo consists of only one floor with an open, diaphanous distribution, with no partitions or rooms and houses no use. The immediate surroundings of the demo will include a paved area.

Program of requirements. None as it has no use.

Characteristic use of the building and other intended uses. The characteristic use is auxiliary building of temporary character. Only occasional visits for dissemination and open labs will be held in the open space, with all other activities such as events, training, conferences or exhibitions taking place inside the Moguda castle, a renovated and refurbished space.

Relationship with the surroundings. The urban environment is defined by a residential area of single-family houses of one or two floors high, the Moguda castle and unbuilt lots. The demo is inside the enclosure of the castle in a wide open area with existent vegetation at the southwest that will be used as sun protection and is in front of the backyards public single-family houses.

5.3.4. Description of the geometry of the building, volume, useful and built surfaces, accesses and evacuation.

Description of the building geometry. The project is developed on one floor. The useful and built surfaces are shown below:

	Interior Surface (m ²)	Built Surface (m ²)
Demo building (ground floor) – phase 1	35,90	40,60
Demo building (ground floor) – phase 2	24,30	28,00
Exterior area – phase 1	-	75,00
Exterior area – phase 2	-	85,84
TOTAL (phase 1)	35,90	115,60

Table 6: Interior and built surface of the Barcelona demo

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The volume of the demo, being open, does not contain volume as such (complying with the restriction of $>75 \text{ m}^3$ according to *Codi 53*). If we consider a hypothetical roof placed at the height where the pillars end it would be $138,8 \text{ m}^3$ for phase 1 (maximum) and 94 m^3 in phase 2.

Access and Evacuation. Vehicle access (and pedestrian access for construction personnel) will be via the Carrer Mogoda road, at the northeast of the Castle enclosure, close to the demo construction area. Pedestrian access for public visits to the demo will be from the main public entrance to the enclosure and Moguda Castle, to the northwest of the plot along the Carrer Mogoda road. The plot has a single boundary of contact with the public space which is where the main entrance is located, Mogoda Road.

There is no wastewater or rainwater evacuation as it will not have water supply facilities or services, nor will it have a roof, being an open structure. However, during the construction process, wastewater will be discharged directly into the existing sewerage system within the plot.

5.4. Obligatory regulations & implications

5.4.1. Permits type and plan

The processing of the necessary permits for the construction of the Barcelona demo will start before June 2025 as they have to be submitted to the city municipality this month at the latest. Usually, the average time for issuance is between one and six months. Regarding the legislative requirements for demonstration is expected to be straightforward as the construction site is INC's own site and the project is small in scale. In this case a short time is expected for obtaining the building permit due to the above but, anticipating possible risks due to delays in its processing (with the consequent delay of the rest of the project planning), it is considered the maximum period of 6 months (longer than usual in the processing of permits for housing constructions in this area).

Due to the type of construction and the actions we are performing on it (construction on protected land and therefore it must be dismantled at the end of the period requested in the permit), two building permits must be requested, as shown below, that will be issued by the relevant municipality of Santa Perpetua de la Moguda.

1. Construction of the demo (by winter of 2025) – Permit 1: construction permit
2. Partial disassembly of the envelope and reconstruction of the modified envelope – no permit needed
3. Total deconstruction of the demo (from spring 2027)– Permit 2: deconstruction permit

5.4.2. Obligatory regulations

We have identified the regulations that are mandatory and/or recommended to be complied with to obtain the building permit for this demo in Santa Perpetua. These regulations are much more lax for this type of construction (auxiliary building) than for the construction of a residential building. Therefore, in this section we show the regulations that will be justified in the technical project or memory of the demo to process the necessary permit and, in the following section, we show in comparison, the regulations and implications that they would have if the same demo was processed but with the use of housing and not of auxiliary temporal building.

- Normes urbanístiques del planejament general de Santa Perpètua (required). Fig 14
- Pla especial de protecció del patrimoni arquitectònic de Santa Perpètua (required). Fig 15.
- Local rule for the protection of areas influenced by the transport of dangerous goods by train²⁴ (not required)
- Código Técnico de la Edificación (CTE) 2022 (not required)
 - CTE: DB SE (required)
- Ley 7/2022, de 8 de abril, de residuos y suelos contaminados para una economía circular, nacional. (required)
- Programa general de prevenció i gestió de residus i recursos de Catalunya (PRECAT20), regional. (required)
- Código Estructural (estructuras hormigón)– CE, Real Decreto 470/2021

²⁴ Resolució INT/2330/2013: Technical instruction of the general directorate of civil protection on the preparation of reports on the minimum conditions to be fulfilled by new urban developments to be located within the areas identified as chemical hazard zones for the transport of dangerous goods by road and rail.

Figure 14. Sta Perpetua's land classification and qualification

Figure 15. Sta Perpetua's areas of archaeological expectation and heritage items

D3 – Protecció de sistemes SUD

D5- desenvolupament en SUD

Figure 16. Sta Perpetua's protected areas.

For its processing are essential: Project description, Specifications and drawings, General budget, Safety and health plan and Waste management plan. It is shown the complete list regarding Code 53 construction type requirements:

- Model of preliminary notification of works
- Technical project: Technical documentation (descriptive and graphic) signed by the competent technician, enclosing verification of the applicable urban planning and sectorial regulations, description of the current situation and brief report of the works, anticipating possible impacts and corrections.
- Certificate issued by the professional body regarding the qualification and authorisation of the competent technician.
- Identification of the actors: builder and owner.
- Photographs of the current status of the site and the status of the existing urbanisation.
- Certificate of acceptance of the waste manager
- Descriptive and graphic information of the cadastral data of the plot.
- Self-assessment of taxes (payment letter).
- Responsible declaration assumed by the construction manager.

And this will be the index of the Technical Project mentioned above:

I. Memorias.

1. Memoria descriptiva.
2. Memoria constructiva
3. Cumplimiento del CTE
 - 3.1. Seguridad Estructural (SE)
4. Cumplimiento de otros reglamentos y disposiciones
 - 4.1 Normativa urbanística Santa Perpetua
 - 4.2 Otras ordenanzas: patrimonio
5. Anejos a la memoria
 - 5.1. Información geotécnica
 - 5.2. Cálculo estructura
 - 5.3. Estudio de Seguridad y Salud
 - 5.3.1. Pliego de condiciones ESS
 - 5.3.2. Presupuesto y medición ESS
 - 5.4 Estudio de Gestión de residuos
 - 5.4.1. Pliego de condiciones EGR
 - 5.4.2. Presupuesto y medición EGR

II. Planos

III. Pliego de condiciones

IV. Mediciones

V. Presupuesto detallado

5.4.3. Obligatory regulations in the processing the building as residential use. Hypothesis for replicability.

We show in comparison, the regulations and implications the same demo would have to assume if it was design for the use of housing and not as auxiliary temporal building. These requeriments are more restricted for residential building than for auxiliary as the residential use has to incorporate performances such as energy efficiency (DB HE regulation), acoustic resistance (DB HR), health and watertightness (DB HS) and a certain fire resistance (DB SI), the latter has not been included in the theoretical proposal. This estimation has been made for the possible replication of the panel in this use mainly. In all cases, for the technical memory of the demo for auxiliary use as well as for the theoretical executive project for residential use, the DB SE (structural safety regulation) had to be complied with and the corresponding calculation for the construction of the prototype (technical memory) will be incorporated. Thus, we establish a theoretical hypothesis where the thermal (and acoustic) insulation of the solution in Barcelona is incorporated and it has been shown graphically in section [3.6 Design of the demo](#). Furthermore, to make the panel replicable, the resistance of the joints and panel will be calculated for the wind resistance corresponding to a fifth floor of a flat on urban land (typical unfavourable maximum) and, the joints will be tested in slabs of 25 and typical spans between pillars of a flat (concrete portico structure).

Regarding this hypothesis, the Executive Project would also had to include also:

3. Cumplimiento del CTE
 - 3.1. Seguridad Estructural (SE)
 - 3.1.6. NCSE-02: Norma construcción sismoresistente
 - 3.2. Seguridad en caso de incendio (SI)
 - 3.3. Seguridad de utilización y accesibilidad (SUA)
 - 3.4. Salubridad (HS)
 - 3.4.1. HS 1: Protección frente a la humedad
 - 3.4.3. HS 3: Calidad del aire interior
 - 3.5. Protección frente al ruido (HR)
 - 3.6. Ahorro de energía (HE)
4. Cumplimiento de otros reglamentos y disposiciones
 - 4.1. Normativa de ámbito estatal
 - 4.1.1. Instalaciones (RITE)
 - 4.1.2. Certificación energética
 - 4.2. Normativa de ámbito autonómico
 - 4.2.1. Habitabilidad Catalunya
 - 4.2.2 Normativa mercancías peligrosas por carretera y ferroviario
 - 4.2.3 Normativa patrimonio y restos arqueológicos
 - 4.2.4 Otras Ordenanzas municipales
5. Anejos a la memoria
 - 5.1. Información geotécnica
 - 5.2. Cálculo estructura
 - 5.3. Eficiencia energética
 - 5.4. Plan de control de calidad
 - 5.5. Estudio de Seguridad y Salud
 - 5.5.1. Pliego de condiciones ESS
 - 5.5.2. Presupuesto y medición ESS
 - 5.6 Estudio de Gestión de residuos

- 5.6.1. Pliego de condiciones EGR
- 5.6.2. Presupuesto y medición EGR
- 5.7 Ficha urbanística

5.5. Description of the demo components

5.5.1. Structural system

Surface foundations are planned, resolved by a foundation slab with a 30 cm edge.

The vertical load-bearing structure consists of 25 x 25 cm reinforced concrete columns with a total height of 3 m, as shown in the structural plans of the project, with a span between columns of 3 m in the longitudinal direction and 4,5 m in the perpendicular direction.

These columns will be tied together by horizontal flat beams, to be defined in the executive project. If structurally it is not necessary, the tie beam will be discarded.

Element	Function	Material	Reinforcement	Improvement from conventional	Quantity
Slab	Surface foundation (in situ)	HA-25 reinforced concrete	Rebar + steel mesh	-100% Recycled coarse aggregate - Alkali-Activated Cement (AAC)	43 m ² 12,9 m ³
Pillars	Vertical structure (in situ)	HA-25 reinforced concrete	Rebar + steel mesh	-100% Recycled coarse aggregate - Alkali-Activated Cement (AAC)	8 pillars 25*25 cm 3 m height 1,5 m ³
Tie Beams	Horizontal structure (in situ)	To be defined in the Technical Project	To be defined in Technical Project	To be defined in Technical Project	8 perimetral beams Section to be defined in the Technical Project

Table 7: Constructive solutions. Structural system

The novel Alkali-Activated Cements (AACs) will be developed progressively during the project to minimize the virgin content by combining CDWs (e.g. recycled aggregates and supplementary cementitious materials) and other industrial wastes (e.g. biomass ash, blast furnace slag, almond husk ash), with the aim to achieve zero virgin content AAC at industrial

scale.²⁵ On the other hand, the project target to increase as much as possible the replacement of virgin aggregates with recycled ones in newly developed AAC concretes. The idea is to exceed the national standard of 20% of recycled coarse aggregates and to verify that this percentage can be extended (possibly up to 100%) without compromising the required performances. The intention is to reduce the mass concrete solution to 50% virgin material as well as, for this solution (regarding KPIs), 65 % recycled content (cement + coarse aggregates).

5.5.2. Envelope system

The façade system will be ventilated façade type and will be composed only of the heavy exterior cladding panels of this system. These façade panels will be precast panels of AAC concrete reinforced with biobased composite bars, floor to roof high, installed on a substructure²⁶. The joints of these panels will be designed to be easy to disassemble, allowing them to be deconstructed. The joints will not be sealed in the demo as they only have a ventilated function and are intended to be demountable. For uses with a need for watertightness, dry seals can be studied and wet seals such as polyurethane seals must be avoided.

Element	Function	Material & reinforcement	Substructure	Improvement from conventional	Quantity
Precast Panels	Exterior cladding for facade (off-site)	Concrete & Biobased composite bars	Stainless Steel	-100% Recycled coarse aggregates - Alkali-Activated Cement (AAC)	30 units 3 * 0,9 m 81 m ²
Façade openings	Door	Open, no door	-	-	Opening of 2,1 * 0,9 m
Roof	Roof to protect from sun and rain	Light roof to be found from second-hand market	To be defined in Technical Project (light solution)	This element is not tested in the project	1 unit To be defined in Technical Project

Table 8: Constructive solutions. Envelope system

The AAC demountable panels of the project have been designed to make it replicable in future housing use. It is the exterior facade cladding, mainly for ventilated facades but it is not limited to these facades. It will not be a sealed system; its function will only be that of exterior cladding as indicated. The main improvements compared to a conventional building

²⁵ Technical information on the newly AAC developed cement in the project will be explained in the document: D2.1 AACC & mortar prototypes

²⁶ Technical information on the precast concrete elements developed in the project will be explained in the document: D 2.2 Precast element prototypes

with the same system, have been to guarantee higher durability than the current ones (biobased composite bars reinforcement instead of conventional steel bars) and to lengthen the lifespan of the panels by making it possible to dismantle them in pieces (removable joints). Biobased bars, in addition to increasing the durability of the panel outdoors, also allow in theory to reduce the thickness of the panel, increasing the material-to-surface ratio. The intention is to reduce at least 60% of virgin material for this solution (regarding KPIs), and incorporate 50 % of recycled content (cement + coarse aggregates). Due to the precast solutions the waste intensity during construction will be 0%.

The conclusion to develop and improve this type of constructive solution was reached after research on the most widespread use of concrete panels in housing and the improvement of the most common problems generated (jointly to their environmental impact), considering the possibilities of this project. After a review of related literature such as the Andece²⁷reports²⁸, most commercial panels currently used in housing are used with self-supporting behaviour (non-load-bearing) with enclosure function, exterior use subjected to external agents (wind, pollution, etc.) and for the blind part of the enclosure. This analysis led us to develop this type of solution for the panels in the project. Although they are most commonly used horizontally, it was finally decided to use a vertical panel for solving the floor-to-ceiling cladding. There are also classifications according to their composition, the most common being concrete with traditional steel reinforcement not with fibres, according to their section, with homogeneous panels (the one developed in the project), multi-layer or alveolar panels and according to their shape, such as flat panels, with relief, wavy, lattice or other configurations. Finally, they can also be classified according to their aesthetic component, with architectural value such as textures or colours or without, such as natural finish panels. In this case, the second option was chosen due to the initial development of these panels, but if they are commercialised after the project, these values could be incorporated.

In addition, the advantages highlighted in the report over precast concrete panels are: speed of execution, minimum reduction of rubble, fire resistance and acoustic insulation (depending on the design of the solution), adaptability of shapes and sizes and variety of finishes, durability of the façade with reduced maintenance, safety on site and elimination of the use of scaffolding.

Two of the problems that often occur in the use of these panels in housing are the appearance of problems concerning durability and their disassembly in pieces. The durability of conventional concrete panels is often limited due to their internal steel reinforcement which, after a relatively short period compared to the life span of a building

²⁷ ANDECE is National Association of the Precast Concrete Industry in Spain.

²⁸ Technical guide to precast concrete facades, 2021 – ANDECE: <https://www.andece.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Guia-Tecnica-Fachadas-prefabricadas-de-hormigon.pdf>

(especially in environments with higher exposure to humidity, marine environment, thawing, etc.), tends to degrade (despite the alkaline coating and protection of the concrete), eventually expanding and damaging the concrete panel (cracks). By replacing the steel reinforcements with bio-based bars, this situation can be solved as they do not have these problems, extending the useful life of the panel. Currently, there are other types of reinforcements in the panels, such as glass or polymeric fibres. These problems can be seen in the following pictures:

Figure 17. patología de paneles prefabricados de hormigón de fachada Orcasitas, Usera, Madrid-
source: Eptisa

The new risk that could arise in the introduction of bio-based rebar as reinforcement would be the difficulty in separating the rebar from the concrete at the end of its useful life to be able to recycle the two materials independently. Currently, steel bars can be easily separated from the concrete using magnets. By proposing that these panels should be demountable and therefore reusable, the aim is to alleviate this problem by extending their life with a second use.

The other key problem with the concrete panels currently available on the market is that they cannot be disassembled in pieces, making it difficult to maintain them individually or to reuse only part of the building façade. Nowadays, as they are dry-laid panels, they are assembled from the lowest floor to the top floor, and can be dismantled in the opposite direction (from top to bottom) in order to be able to dismantle the panel or floor in question that needs to be dismantled. In other words, the entire façade must be dismantled for a panel. Although the systems of disassembly by parts are more widespread in light panels,

such as the Click-&-Go BIPV²⁹ facade system³⁰ for glass PV panels developed by TULiPPS³¹, they are not widely available and used in heavy panels such as concrete panels. Below is shown the current conventional joints of concrete panels as well as an example of a lightweight panel that can be dismantled in pieces from the Click-&-Go system.

Figure 18. Current conventional stainless steel joints for concrete panels. Left: Fixi 3D system³² – source: Fixinox / Right: Anchor systems of Halfen³³ – source: Halfen

All concrete panel connections are similar and consist of: a hanger (vertical), spacer (horizontal), retainer (between panel and panel) and wind anchor (last panel, not connected to another panel). Recognised brands: Halfen, Hilti, Fixinox, etc.

²⁹ <https://bipv.world/>

³⁰ The Click-&-Go BIPV facade is prefabricated with solar panels and delivered as a complete package. This allows for unprecedentedly short installation times with minimal risk of errors. An important functionality of the system is that each individual panel can be easily removed. This is essential for low maintenance costs. Another unique feature is that solar panels and traditional façade materials can be combined in a single mounting system. The Click-&-Go mounting system can be used in every wind zone up to a height of 200 metres.

³¹ <https://www.tulipps.com/>

³² Fixinox: <https://www.fixinox.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/1811-ES-ANCLAJES-PARA-PANELES-DE-HORMIGO%CC%81N-ARQUITECTO%CC%81NICO.pdf>

³³ Halfen: https://www.halfen.com/PDF-Dateien/Druckschriften/Technische%20Produktinformationen/Halfen_FB_23_EN.pdf

Figure 19. Click-&-Go BIPV facade system, demountable by panel – source: TULiPPS & BIPV world

During the design of this demo, we have been researching and contacting experts in panel fixing systems design as well as suppliers of heavy panel connectors to come up with a constructive solution that allows the heavy panels to be disassembled by floors or individually as well as incorporating a certain flexibility for the inclusion of other layers of compliance (insulation, waterproofing sheets) behind the panel. Due to this premise, an initially unconsidered substructure (which also provides flexibility in the dimensional design) has been incorporated to achieve this. All these actions do not limit the design of the interior façade layers of the building, such as the interior cladding or intermediate load-bearing layers. The final design of these demountable joints is still in process and will be detailed in the technical report of the constructed project. If possible these reversible joint components will be sourced from commercially available materials.

Finally, in defining the dimensions of the panel, we took into account, for example, the limitation of normal truck transport, the handiness of the operators (they are equally heavy panels), adaptability to structural housing dimensions, representativeness in the market, the moulds to be obtained by Sorigué, etc. Finally, a maximum height of 3 m and a width of 0.9 m were defined (if the panel were to be turned horizontally, it would be a piece that could also function as a window parapet, railing or upper part of openings, among other reasons).

According to the conventional solid concrete panels for façade in the market, the characteristics are the following. In addition to the technical conditions of compressive and flexible strength, dimensional characteristics, weight and durability, it will also be desirable to test the materials developed within the project at least on the following conditions: thermal conductivity, thermal inertia, acoustic resistance, fire resistance, CO₂ emissions, ease of separation of the components in the mixture and toxicity (among others that may arise during the development of the project). This specification will be interesting to include in the Digital Passport of the Product (DPP) and will be updated in the Technical Project of the demo constructed, with the final results for this design panels.

Thickness (cm)	Mass (kg/m ²)	U (W/m ² K)	C _p (J/kg·K)	Aerial sound insulation (dBA)	Impact sound insulation (dB)	Fire resistance EI
12	300	4.105	1000 ³⁴	51.91	77.30	120 (min)

Table 9: Constructive solutions. Envelope system

For the construction of these panels, the technical guidelines³⁵ developed by ANDECE and ANfhARQ³⁶ will be followed. The photo shows the installation of a concrete panel on a façade.

Figure 20. Lifting a concrete panel on site for its installation – source: ANfhARQ – Casa Mundejo

Façade openings

No windows or doors will be installed. A 2.1 m high and 0.9 m wide opening is planned for access to the interior of the demo.

³⁴ [Prontuary of construction solutions / materials of the Spanish Technical Code \(CTE\)](#)

³⁵ ANDECE guide: : <https://www.andece.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Guia-Tecnica-Fachadas-prefabricadas-de-hormigon.pdf>

ANfhARQ: https://www.andece.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/montaje_fachadas_anfharq_ieca.pdf

³⁶ National association of manufacturers of architectural concrete façades in Spain

Roof

The roof will be a system that will only protect against rain and solar radiation but will not be a closed and watertight system and will be installed with an independent and separate structure from the demo, above it. The first idea was to install a light conventional or sandwich panels but regarding urban regulation, the demo hasn't to be closed and watertight. Finally, economically viable alternatives will be studied like textiles solution, easy to disassemble and supported by a light structure or other possibilities through sourcing and reusing this protection-covering layer from other COMSA construction sites. This envisaged structure can be illustrated graphically in 3.6. Design of the demo.

5.5.3. Partitioning system (partitions or floor slabs between floors)

There will be no interior partitions, it will be an open-plan space.

As it is a one-story demo, there will be no interior horizontal divisions.

5.5.4. Exterior Finishing system

No exterior coating such as paint will be applied to the façade panels.

The path to access the demo together with its direct surroundings will be paved with 75 m² of precast pavement blocks for exteriors. These will be removable AAC-based paving blocks of 20 x 40 cm with the maximum recycled aggregates that can be achieved for blocks, expecting 100%. The intention is to reduce the 90% of virgin material as well as, for this solution (regarding KPIs), 90 % recycled content (cement + aggregates). Due to the removable precast solutions of dry construction, the waste intensity during construction will be 0%. As for the façade panels, a test of the indicated conditions will be also desirable.

Element	Function	Material	Installation	Improvement from conventional	Quantity
Precast blocks	Exterior paving (off-site)	Concrete	Dry system	-100% Recycled aggregates - Alkali-Activated Cement (AAC)	0,2 * 0,4 m 75 m ²

Table 10: Constructive solutions: Finishing systems, exterior

These precast pavement blocks for exterior and pedestrian traffic will be intended to later be included in the commercial catalogue of Sorigué (consortium partner), after the project completion. Below is a sample of one of the conventional paving blocks in the catalogue but which will be analogous in the dimensions and characteristics shown in the sheet provided by Sorigué. The difference will be the use of AAC cement and the recycled aggregates

indicated in the datasheet will be increased to the maximum possible, foreseeing 90% of the total aggregates.

Figure 21. Technical data sheet of the precast pavement blocks. The difference between this current commercial block and the developed in project will be the use of AAC cement and the incorporation of 90% of recycled aggregates, besides 20% – source: Sorigué

5.5.5. Environmental conditioning and service system

Water supply. There is a water supply connection next to the location for the construction of the demo. No water system will be installed in the demo, as the construction has no use but to be a prototype.

Water drainage. No water drainage will be installed in the demo, as the construction has no use but to be a prototype. Rain drainage will be through the derivation and direct filtration to the ground.

Electricity supply and telecommunications. There is an electricity supply connection next to the location for the construction of the demo. No electricity system or telecommunications will be installed in the demo, as the construction is a non-habitable space. However, there is lighting inside the complex.

5.6. Design of the demo

The corresponding graphic information of the demo is shown below. In order, we show the context plan of the intervention (scale 1:1000), the implantation plan (1:250), the demo plan

(1:50), the dimensional plan (1:50), the elevations (1:50) and, finally, the plan where the theoretical compliance with the CTE- HE is incorporated (1:50).

Figure 22. Plan 1:1000. Context of the intervention. The demo is shown in red, inside La Moguda Castle complex, in Sta Perpetua. North is at the top.

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Figure 23. Plan 1:250. Implantation plan, inside La Moguda Castle complex.

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Figure 24. Demo Plan 1:100 – Ground floor

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Figure 25. Dimensional Demo Plan 1:75 – Ground floor

Figure 26. Northeast Elevation Plan 1:75

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Figure 27. Northwest Elevation Plan 1:75

Figure 28. Southeast Elevation Plan 1:75

Figure 29. Southwest Elevation Plan 1:75

Figure 32. Theoretical compliance with the CTE- HE Plan 1:50, Option 2 – Ground floor

Figure 33. Theoretical compliance with the CTE- HE Plan 1:50, Option 3 – Ground floor

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Figure 34. East Axonometry – volume

Figure 35. West Axonometry – volume

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Figure 36. East Axonometry – volume construction, without roof installation

5.7. Construction details

The corresponding graphic information of the demo is shown below. In order, we show the construction detail of the demo that will be built and the construction detail incorporating the hypothetical elements for the use of housing. In this last detail, it is incorporated the needed layers to accomplish the DB HE (energy efficiency performance), DB HR (acoustical performance) and DB HS (health performance). These solutions could change in the definition of the final Technical Project regarding the definitions of the removable connections of the façade panel with the building structure. Currently, they are not designed to be removable per panel but there is the objective to design solutions like the ones described in [3.5.2. Envelope system](#) for the Click & Go panels.

Figure 37. Constructive solution detail 1:25 (pending final definition by type of union)

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Figure 38. Theoretical compliance with the CTE - Constructive solution detail 1:25 (*pending final definition by type of union*)

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5.8. Deconstruction and reversible construction design

5.8.1. Hypothesis

Currently, circularity in the construction sector is mainly focused on the recycling of CDW and less effort is focused on eliminating the root of the problem by adopting design systems and dry construction methods that enable the deconstruction of construction solutions, thus extending the useful life of the elements by allowing their repairability and reuse and, ultimately, minimizing the generation of CDW (prefabricated dry systems). Most of the buildings are still built with traditional on-site or hybrid construction methods where dry solutions are not always removable (apart from not being from materials with "circular" content: recycled or renewable materials).

Circularity considerations are incorporated both in the design, with a proportion of recycled materials, and in the construction methods, utilizing prefabricated, modular, and demountable dry facade components that enable component replacement. To facilitate this process and standardize component recovery practices, a deconstruction manual will be developed for the project. To test this hypothesis of the real deconstruction potential of the demo elements designed, three phases will be developed as you can see in the image:

1. Construction (by winter of 2025)
2. Partial disassembly of the envelope and reconstruction of the modified envelope & monitoring and assessment of this process (by winter 2026)
3. Total deconstruction of the demo (by April 2027)

Figure 39. Second phase: Partial disassembly and assembly of the envelope hypothesis- 1:150

5.8.2. Components

The elements that will be disassembled in phase 2 will be the concrete facade panels and obviously, its substructure.

In phase 3, all the components will be disassembled including concrete facades, exterior pavements and external light roof and, on-site elements (slab, pillars and top beams) will be demolished. Reuse/resale/recycling channels for the dismantled and demolished elements will be explored and conducted, as explained in [3.10.Future of dismantled solutions and construction waste.](#)

5.9. Future of dismantled solutions and construction waste

To achieve the KPI of 0% waste intensity during the construction of the demo, as well as during phase 2 of adaptation of the envelope and the final deconstruction of phase 3; it is necessary to find a destination of waste and the components incorporated through different routes. As it was explained in the section of KPIs, when we refer to waste intensity in this case is understood as a reduction of construction or demolition waste sent to landfill, as these will be sent for recycling and/or reused in other works.

The proposed recovery routes consider the waste hierarchy proposed in the European Directive 2008/98/EC on waste management³⁷. This directive prioritizes reuse routes, followed by the possibility of recycling the material, then the option of backfilling, and the least desirable option is to divert the waste to landfill. Therefore, reuse and recycling in the construction sector will be preferred and high-value applications will be prioritised here. Lower-value applications (such as backfilling) within or outside the construction sector will be examined but adopted only as a last resort. Landfilling is discarded.

³⁷ [Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives.](#)

Figure 40: Waste hierarchy of Waste Framework Directive of EU – source: Waste Framework Directive³⁸ – European Commission.

Excess material and CDW will be generated during the three phases of project execution as shown in the following tables. The initial proposed routes and an approximation of the type and quantities of waste generated are proposed, these being in the process of being created and not being in any case final values of the demos but approximations and intuitive intentions. These tables will be modified with the final results once the three phases of execution of the demo have been carried out and monitored.

Phase 1 – Construction of the demo

Waste generated	Type of waste	LER code	Quantity Expected (of total m ²)	Valorisation route	Final destiny
Excess of materials developed	Dry mixing of concrete, aggregates		1 %	Reuse	Local industry detected by SYNER
	Pavement blocks		>2%	Reuse	Consortium partners works or marketplaces
Construction waste	Concrete grout		10%	Recycling	Local industry detected by SYNER
	Steel bars		5%	Steel Recycling	Local waste manager
	Steel substructure		1%	Steel Recycling	Local industry detected by SYNER
	Cutouts or broken concrete panels		>5%	Concrete mixed Recycling -Biobars?	Local industry detected by SYNER

³⁸ [Waste Framework Directive](#)- European Commission

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	Packaging - plastic		>1%	Plastic Recycling	Local waste manager
	Packaging - pallets		>1%	Wood Recycling	Local waste manager
	Other	-	-	-	-

Table 11: Waste generated during Phase 1 and proposed valorisation routes.

Phase 2 – Partial dismantling and reconstruction of the envelope

Waste generated	Type of waste	LER code	Quantity Expected (of total m ²)	Valorisation route	Final destiny
Excess of materials developed	Concrete panels		>80 %	Reuse	Consortium partners or stakeholders works
	Steel substructure		>80 %	Reuse	Consortium partners or stakeholders works
Deconstruction waste	Cutouts or broken concrete panels		>5%	Concrete mixed Recycling -Biobars?	Local industry detected by SYNER
	Steel substructure		1%	Steel Recycling	Local industry detected by SYNER
	Other	-	-	-	-

Table 12: Waste generated during Phase 2 and proposed valorisation routes.

Phase 3 – Deconstruction of the demo

Waste generated	Type of waste	LER code	Quantity Expected (of total m ²)	Valorisation route	Final destiny
Deconstruction waste	Concrete		100%	Recycling	Local industry detected by SYNER
	Steel bars		100%	Steel Recycling	Local waste manager
	Steel substructure		100%	Reuse	Consortium partners or stakeholders works
	Concrete panels		100%	Reuse	Consortium partners or stakeholders works
	Pavement blocks		100 %	Reuse	Consortium partners works or marketplaces

Waste	Protection coverage		100%	Reuse	To be defined
	Broken panels		>1%	Concrete Recycling -Biobars?	Local industry detected by SYNER
	Broken pavement blocks		>1%	Concrete Recycling	Local industry detected by SYNER
	Other	-	-	-	-

Table 13: Waste generated during Phase 3 and proposed valorisation routes.

These valorisation routes for the excess materials and components produced during the project and the CDW will be studied since November 2024, detected before November 2025 and executed during the three phases of the project. As mentioned above, priority will be given to the reuse of excess components and when this is not possible, the waste will be recycled, leaving backfilling as the last option. The exploitation for reuse will be prioritized in the ongoing commercial construction projects of COMSA, Sorigué and INCASOL and, additionally, opportunities will be sought outside the consortium through the Circular Construction Clusters set up in Barcelona. The type of construction projects selected will depend on the qualities of the material/components and the opportunities available at the time. However, it is intended to cover a range of construction projects such as housing, infrastructure or urban environment in new construction or renovation. For the exploitation opportunities for the recycling of the components, it will be essential to detect the possible industrial applications and the industries interested in this type of waste at the local level.

Monitoring of the material will be carried out during the different phases to obtain the tables proposed here with the results of quantities, type of treatment and final destination. For this, the help of the SYNER platform³⁹, developed by Symbiosis, outside of the construction sector, will be essential. This tool is used for waste classification and detection of possible symbiosis with other industries, which will be fed with local data during this process.

5.10. Emerging Challenges

Every step from the written documentation to the construction of a project implies some changes and adjustments that respond to different technical reasons. During the construction definition of the project pilots, some inconveniences arose that had to be solved by considering and resolving different alternatives.

- Conditions of the materials to be used: as described in 3.5, the reinforced concrete to be used in the Barcelona pilot project for the façade uses an experimental type of

³⁹ SYNER is a platform developed by Symbiosis: <https://synerplatform.com/>

cement with reduced CO₂ emissions, while the steel has been replaced by bio-based bars used to make the reinforcements, which also reduce greenhouse gas emissions. However, these alternatives have some other aspects to consider, such as their availability on the market for mass use, the repercussions they may have on construction costs and other environmental impacts that may be significant, such as the toxicity emitted.

- Limited use of prefabrication techniques: in the first instance, it was considered the possibility of carrying out all the construction components of the pilot project through offsite prefabrication, transfer to the site and dry assembly. Subsequently, considering that the part where configuration changes, material recovery and reuse of materials will be tested is mainly the façade panel subsystem, it was decided that the main structure (foundations and columns) should be built on site. This also makes it easier to meet deadlines and execution costs and it is aligned with the conventional construction in Europe.
- Limitations of the pilot and its representative prototype: any construction pilot that intends to represent a much larger set of constructions may have restrictions that could affect its representation. In the case of the Barcelona pilot, its location must be taken into account (for more information see 3.3), since it is located in a historic site with heritage protection (the Castle of Santa Perpètua de Mogoda) and is not in an urbanised environment. This location means that there are no adjacent buildings or the usual construction resources in the immediate vicinity, which implies certain logistical restrictions that will be overcome by a greater impact of the use of transport and other auxiliary equipment.
- Integration of the vision of the different actors in the design stage: the WP4 sphere of collaboration and especially its pilot design (as described in 3.2) bring together several actors coming from different companies, fields of work, professional backgrounds and experiences that shape their vision about sustainability, environmental valuation of materials and how to implement the circular economy in construction. This background means different points of view that have not completely coincident among all the participants in the pilot, so different discussions have been held to determine the construction solutions that, in addition to meeting the requirements of the project, have sufficient consensus.
- Potential uses to be represented and actual uses of the prototype: another point of interest is how a total construction (the potential application of the pilot design in residential buildings that meet all regulatory requirements) could be represented through the materialization of a part of it (the part that is built in the prototype, which by its own limitations lacks some constructive subsystems). This was discussed at length by the members of the pilot team, and it was established that the main structure, the façade panel system and the interior and exterior floorings must be designed to be hypothetically completed with other layers and construction components required for housing use (thermal insulation, waterproofing, interior finishes...).

- Compliance with building and heritage regulations: experimental construction is not always considered by building regulations and this is the case for Spanish regulations. To avoid the requirements of the Spanish Technical Building Code making the design, construction, modification and deconstruction of the pilot more complex, costly and time-consuming than foreseen for a temporary, experimental construction, the dialogue with the public administration to obtain construction authorization focused on the pilot's non-permanent, partial and non-habitable construction conditions (see 3.3.2 & 3.4). Similarly, some difficulties arose due to the legal protection of the property on which the pilot is located as a historic site of heritage value. In this case the difficulties arose from the fact that the excavations to be carried out might require, depending on their depth, the intervention of an archaeologist and other considerations for the protection of archaeological remains (see also 3.4). This was remedied by the design of a shallow foundation that was part of the dialogue with the public administration.
- Concerning the initial proposal & planning, some aspects not initially considered arose in the project because of not previously defined new elements in the construction as:
 - o Need for a geotechnical report for structural justification despite the small nature of the demo.
 - o Role of the architect within the partners - signature of collegiated architect
 - o Final need for steel substructure for the facade panels to facilitate their disassembly and flexibility of placement.
 - o Impossibility of finding a roof within the consortium partners' works for reuse (sandwich panels). Need to look for an alternative to roofing as a light protection from suppliers outside the consortium.

In addition to the solving of specific problems, the above points led to the development of a methodology for the solution of possible barriers. This methodology, based on teamwork led by the WP4 leader, consisted basically in the detection of problems, the search for solutions by the partners according to their relationship with each area (location, materials, construction techniques, intended uses, legal permissions...), decision making in plenary meetings and, finally, their resolution by different actors according to their knowledge of the subject under discussion. Finally, the possible list of risks were mitigated: Risk 4 is overcome with the demo site available.

5.11. Improvement over conventional buildings

The project has five clear objectives, which represent substantial improvements in the circularity of the materials designed, manufactured and constructed in the project, compared with a conventional cast-in-place concrete and precast concrete panel, as they consider all phases of the life cycle of a building. In the construction sector, the key to closing the materials loop is not only found in specific materials, in a construction system or building,

but in the management of resources throughout their life cycle. The objectives are reducing new extraction resources, reducing CO₂ emissions of concrete, reducing CDW⁴⁰, design for deconstruction and control and management of installed materials during their use.

At the stage of extraction and manufacture of the materials (A1-A3⁴¹, D):

- **Reduce the extraction of new virgin material** and therefore encourage the use of recycled materials, by:
 - the replacement of coarse aggregates in concrete with recycled aggregates
 - the replacement of ordinary Portland cement with recycled alternatives (from other industries, reducing its waste) – AAC cement⁴²
 - KPI associated - Virgin content in the building: 50% + Reusable and/or recyclable content: 80%

- **Reduce the environmental impact of CO₂ emissions** in one of the sectors that produce the most in construction, namely cement & concrete, through:
 - Replace ordinary Portland cement with low-carbon alternatives, either recycled or bio-based *
 - Optimization of the structural design, reduction of thicknesses to a minimum without losing the necessary performances + materials efficiency
 - Raw or recycled materials sourced locally and from national industries
 - KPI associated - Locally available content: 100%

- **Design for deconstruction:**
 - reversible joint components easy to disassemble by parts or pieces
 - enable the separation of materials within the same product to be managed separately in the waste management stage
 - KPI associated - Waste intensity during construction: 0%

⁴⁰ Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW)

⁴¹ These letters refer to the nomenclature of the life cycle stages of a building for its life cycle analysis (LCA). Nomenclature A refers to the stage of extraction, construction, transportation to the construction site and construction of the building. The B nomenclature refers to the use stage of the building, which includes maintenance, repair, replacement of materials, as well as the use of energy and water necessary to give service to the building. The C nomenclature refers to the end of its life cycle which includes the dismantling or demolition of the building/materials and its corresponding waste management and treatment. Stage D refers to the benefits and loads of the materials beyond the end of the building's useful life. This methodology is explained in the European standard EN15804.

⁴² RECONSTRUCT will develop and produce a range of circular AACs using as raw materials by-products and wastes that haven't been used before at commercial scale (biomass ash, CDW, blast furnace slag, weld slag, silica fume, glass waste) with the aim to achieve full substitution of the virgin content. The novel AAC formulas are intended to achieve 80% reduction of embodied carbon compared to OPC while performing equally or better than OPC in key performance indicators (durability, strength, etc.) and at lower costs due to the lower cost of the secondary raw materials.

- Hypothesis for deconstruction: Dry constructive systems allow dismantability and therefore, adaptability of the building space and materials maintenance/substitution
- Limits of the improvement strategies:
 - Sometimes strategies to improve one indicator have a negative influence on others. In this case it is possible, pending verification during this project, that the replacement of ordinary Portland cement with other alkaline-based alternatives will lead to a reduction in CO₂ emissions but an increase in the toxicity indicator.
 - In the first stages of the project, the strategy of structural optimization was an important premise in the reduction of the thickness of the slab in contact with the ground (<20cm) and the quantity of material, such as not including a substructure for the façade panels. Initially, the heavy panels were not to include a substructure and were attached with direct anchors to the load-bearing structure like commercial systems, which hindered the possible individual panel or intermediate floor dismantling and limited the structural and façade design. Finally, during the design of the joints of the facade panels to the structure, we found that to enable the dismantling of the panels individually, it will be necessary to place a substructure with a certain manoeuvrability and therefore, increasing the thickness of the slab is favourable. In addition, to test this dismantability between hypothetical intermediate floors of a residential building (replicability at higher heights of buildings where horizontal joints arise between floors), these horizontal joints will also be designed, resulting finally in a slab thickness of 25 cm, as the minimum conventional intermediate slabs of housing.

At the stage of construction of the components on site (A5⁴³):

- **Reduce waste generated during construction** by:
 - Incorporation of prefabricated panels made in the factory and dry-installed
 - Optimización de la construcción in situ and material efficiency
 - KPI associated - Waste intensity during construction: 0%
- **Improve waste management** by:
 - Reincorporate the excess of material/pieces from dry construction systems in marketplaces for reclaimed materials or in building sites ongoing of the consortium partners
 - Reintroduce the construction waste from in situ concrete in the recycling loop of recycling centres or other local industries detected in the SYNER platform
 - KPI associated - Waste intensity during construction: 0%
- Limits of the improvement strategies:

⁴³ Refer to Note 25

- During the design of the demo, it was thought to make dry, demountable and reusable foundations as the site is a protected area and the permitted use is only temporary with dismantling at the end of the project. Finally, it comes back to the idea of the intention to demonstrate several different systems (in Brussels it will be demountable foundations) and to test improvements on the most common construction methods nowadays, being the in-situ concrete foundations.

At the stage of use of the building (B2-B5):

- **Increase the durability of the incorporated solutions**, in particular, precast concrete panels as exterior cladding by:
 - Replace steel reinforcement with bio-based bars reinforcement
- **Control and performance management of installed materials/systems** by:
 - Tracking and tracing with digital twinning in BIM (Digitalization)
- Limits of the improvement strategies:
 - Sometimes strategies to improve one indicator have a negative influence on others. In this case, the attempt to increase the durability of the exterior concrete panels by replacing their metal reinforcement with a biobar one, which entails fewer pathologies, may end up making it difficult to separate this reinforcement from the concrete, complicating its recycling by materials at the end of its useful life. Even so, the intention to increase their durability⁴⁴ and to design their assembly-disassembly connections to make their deconstruction and reuse possible, justifies this decision.

At the end-of-life stage of the building - deconstruction and waste management (C1-C4):

- **4. Reduce waste to landfill and promote the recyclability and reuse of materials** once the useful life of the building has reached, through:
 - Selective demolition:
 - reversible joint components easy to disassemble by parts or pieces
 - facilitate the separation of materials within the same product to enable recycling
 - Reincorporate the deconstructed materials systems in marketplaces for reclaimed materials or building sites ongoing of the consortium partners
 - Reintroduce the demolished materials in the recycling loop

To evaluate these objectives and the scope of the implemented strategies, a calculation of the KPIs of the elements built within the demo will be made: foundation slab, vertical

⁴⁴ It is assumed that they will have superior years than the current durability, assuming they do not break due to physical (not chemical) causes.

structure, facade panels and exterior pavement; which excludes the possible pergola or light covering that may be installed to protect the prototype from rain and sun. The sum of the KPIs of each element will evaluate our final result of the building. It is pre-assessed, in accordance with the elements defined in the section [3.5.Description of the demo components](#), the following results:

1. Virgin content in building: 50%
2. Reusable and/or recyclable content: this KPI will depend on the development of WP2: the resistance tests and performance of this type of cement with recycled aggregates.
3. Locally available content: still can be defined – the WP2 is working on it
4. Waste intensity during construction: still can be defined – the WP4 will be working on the derivation routes for reducing to 0 waste to landfill.
5. Material-to-surface ratio: WIP⁴⁵
6. For the façade panels, we have included: a 50% increase in the lifetime of components compared to existing solutions.

For the environmental impact assessment analysis of various indicators in WP5 and for the comparative KPI 5 (material-to-surface ratio), a baseline building has been defined for the Barcelona demo, being an equivalent building but built with conventional techniques and materials of that region. In this way, a reference value for KPI no. 5 can be taken and the improvements of the demo compared to a baseline building can be calculated, checking the improvements proposed in the present section and possibly in the WP5 evaluations (LCA, LCC, circularity, etc.). The baseline building has the same dimensions and construction chapters of the demo (foundations, vertical structure, façade and external paving) but with the following conventional elements:

- Foundation and vertical structure: concrete with rebar reinforcement but without recycled aggregates, of Portland cement and without optimised sections.
- Façade: concrete panels but without recycled aggregates, made of Portland cement and with steel reinforcement, without a demountable system.
- Exterior paving: Concrete pavers but without recycled aggregates, with Portland cement and dry installed.

5.12. Next steps

The next steps will be to develop some aspect still under definition to complete the Technical Project, planned from January 2025 to June 2025, the digitalisation of the demo, its construction and CDW management. The aspects that are in the process of final definition are:

⁴⁵ Work in progress

Before completing the Technical Project to get the building permit:

- Validation with external stakeholders of the final demo design and the methodologies to evaluate the technical indicators & environmental impacts.
- Research and interview with experts and actual providers of fixing systems to arrive at the final design of the removable connections (substructure, anchors) of the façade panels to the structure; to be dismantled by pieces.
- The constructive solutions details, depending on the final design of the fixing system and final Construction Budget and measurements.
- Research and contact with the final suppliers that will provide the connectors of the façade panels
- Research for a light roofing/ pergola
- Obtain a signed commitment from an authorised waste manager for the demo
- Digitalisation of the demo in BIM, under the requirements previously established (in T4.2) so that it can operate with methodologies and digital product passport developed in WP3 and support the environmental impact assessments of WP5. By June 2024.

To realise the future environmental assessment and deconstruction hypothesis will be first necessary to digitalise the demo into BIM models and create a digital twin that tracks and monitors the process. These models will include passports of the materials and products created in the process as well as some commercial systems that will be used in the demos. The digital tools developed in the project will be populated with demonstrator data to enable the calculation of the buildings', components' and materials' circularity performance and short-term environmental and economic impacts. Simulations using alternative design/usage parameters will allow the estimation of long-term impacts based on scenarios regarding material used, building design, component's second life, and technological uptake.

After obtaining the building permit, directly related to the demos:

- Detect the final destination of Construction and Demolition "Waste" (materials and components), starting from December 2024 with the help of the digital platform SYNER⁴⁶ (T4.5) – further explained in 3.10 Future of dismantled solutions and construction waste.
- Assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts (WP5)
- Seek forms of exploitation, among others, identify stakeholders interested in commercialising the façade panels developed. To this end, the necessary tests of technical and performance characteristics (such as fire resistance, conductivity,

⁴⁶ SYNER is a platform developed by Simbiosy: <https://synerplatform.com/>

chemical agents, etc.) should be carried out. It would be interesting to obtain the CE marking if the product is finally commercialised after the project.

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6. Brussels demo. Design & concept.

6.1. Actors, roles and responsibilities

The actors involved in the development of the demo are defined according to their role within the project as shown in the table below.

Building owner	Green Energy Park (GEP)
Designer Manager	Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB)
Execution Manager (construction & deconstruction)	Holland Composites
The management and budgeting necessary for the building permits fees	Green Energy Park (GEP)
Materials and components development	Centro Tecnológico de la Construcción Región de Murcia (CTCON), Università Politecnica delle Marche (UNIVPM), Holland Composites, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB)
BIM model implementer	Holland Composites
Recovery / reuse routes to divert CDW and produced surpluses	Simbiosi Industrial S.L., Societat Orgànica +10 SCCL
LCA, LCC and circularity/adaptability analysis	Instituto de Tecnología de la Construcción de Cataluña (ITEC), Societat Orgànica +10 SCCL

Table 14: Actors involved in the development of the Brussels demo

Green Energy Park (GEP) is the client, landowner and end-user of the building. With the help of the department of Infrastructure at the VUB, they will manage the permit application process and coordinate the construction activities.

Holland Composites (HOL) is the industrial partner in charge of the production and assembly of the modular, prefabricated building structure. They will also output the BIM-model to test the Reconstruct digital workflow.

Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) will develop, test and deliver the new, low-carbon TRC and AAC-based floor components, that will be demonstrated in the pilot.

Societat Orgànica (SOO) will conduct the circularity (and adaptability) analyses to assess the impact of the developed solutions, relative to current building practices.

6.2. Design Process

Through an iterative approach, three elements have come together in the design of the Brussels demo: the context and **characteristics of the site location**, the **programmatic requirements** formulated by the user, Green Energy Park, and the **modular, off-site building approach of Holland Composites** using prefabricated, lightweight sandwich elements. In the following chapters, we will give a chronological overview of the design steps taken for the Brussels demo and the lessons learnt along the way.

In September 2023, the demo partners gathered for a kick-off in Lelystad, the Netherlands, for a **guided visit to Holland Composites' production facilities** and their **Qbix demo pavilion** on-site. The meeting allowed Holland Composites to outline their vision on sustainable building, using lightweight prefab sandwich elements, branded as Duplicor⁴⁷, with a **foam core of recycled PET** and **bio-resin shells** to drastically reduce carbon-intensity, and a **modular off-site building approach**, the Qbix building system⁴⁸, to allow the disassembly and reuse of their components.

⁴⁷ [Duplicor - Bio-based fire resistant composite](#)

⁴⁸ [Duplicor - Bio-based fire resistant composite](#)

Figure 41. Kick-off at Holland Composites in Lelystad, 2023 – source: VUB

Figure 42. The Qbix demo pavilion under construction: assembly of the hybrid façade structure and the sandwich floor elements, 2023 – source: Holland Composites

The Qbix system was designed specifically for the healthcare sector, and it works well for **single-storey buildings**. In the years to come, Holland Composites wants to expand the system to **multi-storey applications**. In that case, the storey floors will have to meet higher requirements in terms of **load capacity, fire resistance and acoustic insulation**, making concrete the more obvious material choice over lightweight PET foam.

Based on the use case of Holland Composites, VUB will develop a **new, concrete sandwich element**, that goes beyond current practices in the sector. Combining **textile-reinforced concrete shells** and an **alkali-activated concrete core**, to goal of the demo partners is to drastically minimise **material use** and **GHG emissions** of the component, to assess its **feasibility** and **viability** as a commercial solution and bring it to the market.

At the kick-off, Holland Composites presented the **first SolidWorks model** of the demo, translating the initial sketches in the research proposal to the design language of the Qbix ecosystem. At this stage, the model was still designed without knowing the physical context of the building location, but it gave a good idea of its scale and proportions. It also illustrated

the 170x340 design grid used for the Duplicor elements, the hybrid façade concept and the finishing materials available.

Figure 43. The original sketches in the Grant Agreement, 2023 – source: VUB

Figure 44. The first iteration of the demo design in SolidWorks, 2023 – source: Holland Composites

To guide the design process, VUB established a **work plan** with a sequence of demo meetings and a **project brief** to keep track of the most important variables. Between Societat Orgànica (the Barcelona leader) and Vrije Universiteit Brussel (the Brussels leader), **biweekly coordination meetings** were organised to oversee the activities for the demos, pointing out any challenges we encountered, and monitoring consistency and complementarity between the two approaches.

6.3. Description of the demo

6.3.1. Context

The Belgian demonstrator will be constructed on the premises of **Green Energy Park**, an innovation campus located in Zellik (Brussels), established in collaboration between Vrije Universiteit Brussel and the Brussels University Hospital.

Green Energy Park is a new hub for **multidisciplinary collaboration** providing strategic facilities for research, development and demonstration of advanced technologies. The **Living Lab Centre** of Green Energy Park provides large-scale, real-life environments where companies, knowledge institutions, governments and end users can advance new sustainable solutions in four key areas: energy & mobility, hospital of the future, smart regions and biotechnology. The Living Labs are complemented by a **training, knowledge, and experience centre** to bring innovations to the market faster.

Figure 45. Location and key research domains at the Green Energy Park

The first Living Lab established at Green Energy Park is the **Smart Village Lab**, a real-life testing ground for energy district concepts, combining smart and sustainable control systems at the building level with collective grids exchanging electrical and thermal energy at neighbourhood scale.

The **Reconstruct demo** is the second pilot project on this site and will complement the energy efficiency focus of the Smart Village Lab with a focus on circular economy solutions like low-carbon materials and the reuse of prefab building components. Together, the two initiatives will show the way towards a zero-emissions economy in 2050.

Figure 46. Implantation of the demo on Green Energy Research Park

6.3.2. Client requirements

In the project brief, Green Energy Park specified their **programme of requirements** and the **technical standards** to be met for the various building systems. The two floors of the building are modest in scale and will therefore be programmed as multi-purpose spaces. The one on the **ground floor** will be set up for **meetings and presentations**, and is equipped with a toilet and a wardrobe for coats and presentation material. The one on the **first floor** will be used for more informal activities like **lunch breaks and receptions**, and it comes equipped with a small kitchen block and enough wall area for poster exhibitions.

This way, the demo will be a perfect fit for **guided tours and stakeholder workshops** during the Reconstruct project. After that, and without many interventions, the demo will serve as an **onsite working and meeting space** for GEP, linked to the Smart Village Lab.

A **budget overview** was made to see the split between the partners. From the tables, it became clear that Green Energy Park had budgeted for the interior furnishing of the demo, but not for the architectural assignment, nor the groundworks, fixed furniture or building services. This budget gap was promptly addressed, with GEP organising a meeting with the **Department of Infrastructure** of the University around mid-November. The department agreed to delegate a member of their team to follow up on the project, coordinate the permit

application process and manage the budget, making sure that nothing gets in the way of the demo's completion.

6.3.3. Location on the building site

In November 2023, VUB and GEP gathered at the Green Energy Park in Zellik to decide on the exact **location for the demo**. Master planning for the campus was still ongoing and different locations to the east or north of the Smart Village Lab were considered.

Locating the demo at the **north side of the Smart Village Lab** was found to be optimal in terms of orientation and visibility. It is also a location that is easy to access with construction equipment and allows the building to be connected to existing utilities.

Figure 47. The location of the Brussels demo, adjacent to the Smart Village Lab, 2023 – source: Green Energy Park

Based on the programme and the final location, VUB designed a **second iteration of the demo**, based on five 1.7 x 3.4 m modules, with the long facades facing north and south, which is ideal for office use. This way, more extensive glazing can be provided in the north façade, opening views to the landscape and letting lots of daylight in without excessive heat gains. In turn, the south façade will be more closed to shield the building from the summer heat. With one opening, it will provide a clearly articulated entry on the street side.

Figure 48. The new design concept, based on location and typology, 2023 – source: VUB

6.4. Obligatory regulations & implications

6.4.1. Building permit

A meeting between Green Energy Park and the **Municipality of Asse** was organised at the beginning of December to present the proposal and validate the legal requirements for the building permit. Feedback was positive.

Submission of the **building application** is scheduled for the end of March 2024. Processing by the Municipality normally takes **three months**, so we expect to have a **permit** by the end of June 2024, right before the summer break. By then the **detailed design** (for production and construction) will also be finished.

6.4.2. Obligatory regulations

Green Energy Park falls under the urban development regulations outlined in a regional spatial implementation plan called “**Demarcation of the VSGB (Flemish strategic area around Brussels) and contiguous open space areas**⁴⁹”. It is designated as a “**Specific regional business area for science park**” and belongs to the zoning category 'business activity'. Here are the relevant articles applicable to the Research Park:

Article B8.9.1

⁴⁹ Demarcation of the VSGB and contiguous open space areas, Department of environment of Flanders: <https://dsi.omgeving.vlaanderen.be/fiche-detail/cf4f1055-e9fe-490f-a2b7-278768fc073d>

The business area is zoned for businesses whose main activity is fundamental and/or applied research, and/or development in connection with education and training activities. In addition, the following activities are permitted: service companies providing support to companies carrying out fundamental and/or applied research; renewable energy generation or energy recovery installations.

The following main activities are not permitted: autonomous offices; retail trade; conference facilities.

Article B8.9.2

All operations that are necessary or useful for the realisation of the zoning are permitted in so far as they take into account economical use of space. At least consideration shall be given to the optimal use of the plots, but taking into account security obligations; the possibility of accommodating certain services in common buildings on the business park; the grouping and organisation on the business park of parking facilities for users and visitors.

Common and complementary facilities, inherent to the functioning of the mixed regional business park, are permitted. Facilities for housing security personnel of up to 200 m² floor area, integrated into the commercial building, are permitted. If it is necessary for the security of the security personnel, non-integration is permitted.

Green infrastructure should be integrated into the science park because of the proximity of the habitat directive area 'Laarbeek Forest' located in the Brussels Capital Region.

Figure 49. Land classification for the Research Park

The documents to be compiled for the permit are:

- implantation plan
- ground plans
- section
- terrain profile
- facade drawing
- 6 photographs
- descriptive note
- legend

6.5. Description of the demo components

The **Duplicor façade panels** are 150 mm thick with a U-value of 0,23 W/m²K. They are sandwich elements combining two 3 mm Duplicor laminate shells, made of glass fiber and bio-resin with a 150mm core made up of 3 layers of ArmaPET Eco50 closed cell insulation foam. Composed by:

- 20 mm timber cladding on rails
- 3 mm Duplicor glass fibre laminate
- 150mm core made up of 3 layers of ArmaPET Eco50 closed cell insulation foam
 - $\Lambda = 0,035 \text{ W/mK}$

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- 100% recycled content: PET-bottle waste stream
- fully recyclable (as opposed to alternatives like PUR, ...)
- 3 mm Duplicor glass fibre laminate
- Qbix® Front interior wall system
 - Panel structure
 - Unilin 18 mm FR fibre board

The steel structure on the other hand will have a very substantial amount of embodied emissions and it is crucial to re-use or recycle them at the end of their lifetime.

6.6. Design of the demo

Based on the programme and the final location, as outlined in [4.3.3 Location on the building site](#), VUB designed a **second iteration of the demo**, based on five 1.7 x 3.4 m modules, with the long facades facing north and south, which is ideal for office use. This way, more extensive glazing can be provided in the north façade, opening views to the landscape and letting lots of daylight in without excessive heat gains. In turn, the south façade will be more closed to shield the building from the summer heat. With one opening, it will provide a clearly articulated entry on the street side.

Figure 50. Ground floor of the second iteration of the Brussels demo – source: VUB

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Figure 51. First floor of the second iteration of the Brussels demo – source: VUB

In the plans above, the floor elements with a green dot will have TRC shells from phase one. In phase two, at least one of them will be replaced with a TRC+AAC element.

Based on the new plans, Holland Composites made a second model of the geometry in SolidWorks to make final decisions. The exact **window composition** will be further refined to take natural ventilation and sun shading into account, and a final selection of the **façade materials** will be made, considering aesthetic qualities, environmental impact and potential for disassembly and reuse. The project is then ready to apply for a building permit.

Figure 52. SolidWorks model of the second design: with five modules, a more open façade facing north, and a more closed façade facing south – source: Holland Composites

6.7. Deconstruction and reversible construction design

To test the reversible design of the demo there will be two phases, explained in the following points.

- **Phase 1:** Construction of the 4 storey floor elements with TRC shells, available on the market, instead of the bio-resin shells – starting in April 2025
- **Phase 2:** Replacement of one of the storey floor elements with the new TRC+AAC sandwich panel- starting June 2026

6.7.1. Design for Deconstruction and Reuse

By itself, the hybrid façade concept used in the Qbix system already makes it easy for **interior finishes** and **façade elements** to be disassembled, reused and replaced. The façade elements don't carry any of the building weight, and the building services, passing through the interior layer of the steel structure, are kept separate from the thermal core, making them functionally independent.

Nonetheless, the current structural concept does not allow for **floor elements** to be taken out without deconstructing the structure above. Because each column rests on the floor element below, taking out a floor element implies taking away all structural elements above. The experiment in the demo will be **to change that structural logic**, making the steel columns continuous and supporting the floor elements with a secondary structure of steel L-beams to keep the floor elements accessible for replacement.

Figure 53. Concept with the new structural logic, keeping the floor elements accessible for replacement – source: Holland Composites

With a small spider crane, it should then be possible in phase two of the demo to **replace the original floor element** (with only the TRC shells), with the new floor element (combining the TRC shells with an AAC core) **without removing the upper floor** - as was originally devised in the research proposal. This will make the exercise more representative for cases where changes in the floor layout are required in a multistorey, tertiary building, **with access typically limited to the façade**.

Figure 54. Example of a spider crane, used to lift glass or complete windows up to 3 stories high – source: topwerf.be

To take out the floor element, two **façade elements** will have to come off, which is something already considered in the Qbix system. Additionally, and to make sure the replacement will work, the **columns** of the upper floor of the demo will also be designed in two parts to allow their disassembly from the outside, as sketched in the concept drawing above.

6.7.2. Design for Change

Spatial adaptability. A first exercise that VUB undertook on this topic was to look at how the Qbix system, when scaled to multi-storey applications, can work as a kit of parts to create **flexible plan layouts** allowing for versatility, convertibility and expandability. In multi-storey configurations, the concept with the hybrid façade and the lightweight foundations will meet its limits, and larger building services will have to be fitted. The hybrid façade concept will then probably evolve into a (more traditional) column structure, separate from the façade construction, with flat storey floors either supported on the columns directly in the four corners (as in Qbix today), or on secondary beams, integrated between the columns (as in the demo).

Figure 55. Two possible implementations of the Qbix building system in a 15m multi-storey configuration, using beams and floor elements with different spans (3,4 and 5,1 m) to create flexible plan layouts – source: VUB

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From the exercise, we can conclude that the **first option** allows for easier distribution of building services like ductwork as it creates flat ceilings, but it does not allow for the storey floors to be removed to create new, vertical connections or double-height spaces. The **second option** puts beams in the way of building services but allows taking out separate floor elements for vertical flexibility. In this case, primary distribution can be bundled in a central corridor and then distributed between the structural lines to the assignable areas.

A second challenge was to see how the concrete floor elements could be kept accessible, despite the many technical layers above and below them. **Two possible implementations of functional layering** were proposed for the storey floors, one low-tech, and one high tech, going beyond Qbix’s hybrid facade solution for the distribution of building services.

Low-tech

- natural air supply through window vents
- air exhaust through building service area
- low-temperature radiators or airco units for heating
- raised floor system for cable routing only
- sanitary installations limited, in part, to the building service areas
- thermal mass available for inertia
- rail-mounted lighting

High-tech

- raised floor system for cable routing, mechanical air supply and convectors
- sanitary installations possible throughout
- thermal mass available for inertia
- rail-mounted lighting

Figure 56. Two possible implementations of functional layering for the storey floors, one low-tech, one high tech, going beyond Qbix's hybrid facade solution for the distribution of building services – source: VUB

As in a typical tertiary project, three aspects were considered: providing room for **building services**, keeping **thermal mass** accessible for inertia and providing soft surfaces for **acoustics**. In this case, these requirements also had to be combined with the desire **to keep the floor element untouched and accessible for reuse**.

6.8. Future of dismantled solutions and construction waste

No waste will be created at the material level during the replacement of the floor element. The original TRC + PET component will be disassembled as a whole and taken back by Holland Composites for **reuse in one of their commercial projects**. Because it has the standard Qbix dimensions, this should be easy to do.

On the other side, the plastic and wooden packaging of the components will be managed as construction site waste and separated into two containers and sent for recycling by waste management companies.

6.9. Improvement over conventional buildings

Although very modest in size, the demo is designed to showcase as many **climate and circular economy strategies** as possible, demonstrating how they can converge to achieve a more material-efficient, zero-emissions economy by 2050.

6.9.1. Operational emissions

Building envelope. To lower the operational **energy demands** of the demo, passive design measures are being implemented, combining building compactness with proper solar orientation, optimal insulation, and an airtight enclosure. A mechanical ventilation system with heat recovery will ensure comfort and indoor air quality through the coldest months of the year, while summer comfort will be guaranteed using sun blinds and operable windows for natural cross ventilation.

Building services. Fossil-free, energy-saving building services are implemented to reduce the final energy consumption. Initially, a multi-split air-to-air heat pump will be installed with a very low GWP refrigerant. Cooling will be entirely designed out. Over the longer term, the building will be connected to the (experimental) **district heating** planned for the Green Energy Park, as part of the Smart Village Lab research project.

With the Brussels demo, the Reconstruct team also wants to excel in the three strategies, commonly adopted as part of a **circular design approach**: applying materials with low embodied emissions, designing for change, and allowing for deconstruction and reuse. We go through each of these strategies in the next chapters.

6.9.2. Embodied emissions

Embodied emissions can be reduced in different ways: by improving **structural efficiency**, by replacing mineral or fossil-based materials with **bio-based materials**, by using materials with **recycled content** or by reusing **reclaimed components**.

Structural and material efficiency is well considered: the core concept of the Qbix system is to be as lightweight as possible, using a slim, steel structure to absorb only the normal forces. Lateral rigidity is provided by the sandwich panels for the façades and floors, and they are the only elements where deflection must be accounted for under bending forces.

The **steel structure** is resting on small, removable concrete blocks, readily available on the construction market, placed on a 170 x 170 grid to align with each corner of the floor elements. They can be reused after deconstruction.

Figure 57. schematic of concept for the demonstrator, (a) lightweight structural frame made of steel beams and columns, resting on concrete blocks (b) placement of the wall panels that can be replaced without compromising the structural integrity of the frame – source: Holland Composites

To produce the Duplicor sandwich panels for the façades, **bio-based and recycled materials** are combined to reach a minimal environmental footprint. The sandwich elements have **bio-based shells** and a structural **foam core** based on 100% recycled PET material from drinking bottles. Because of its thermoplastic nature, it is also 100% recyclable.

The **façade elements** are 85 cm wide and form the smallest element in the Qbix design grid. They combine two 3 mm Duplicor laminate shells, made of glass fiber and bio-resin with a 15 cm core made up of 3 layers of ArmaPET Eco50 closed cell insulation foam. The U-value achieved is 0,23 W/m²K, which complies nicely with the regional EPBD regulations.

Figure 58. Model of the current Qbix building system, showing the foundation concept and the hybrid façade structure – source: Holland Composites

In Holland Composites' commercial projects today, the sandwich elements for the **storey floors** are normally made from the same materials. In this case, however, what we want to test is how to comply with the technical requirements for a multistorey setup using circular alternatives for a conventional concrete slab.

To lower GHG emissions, compared to conventional concrete, the high emissions Ordinary Portland Cement will be replaced with **alkaline-activated concrete made with by-products from secondary sources**. Conventional steel reinforcements will be replaced with **textile reinforcements** to reduce the thickness of the concrete shells to about 3 cm, thus reducing material intensity.

Finally, for some elements of the building like the concrete foundation blocks, exterior landscaping, rail lighting and furniture, VUB will reach out to local stakeholders in their network to find **reclaimed components** in the months to come. Success cannot be guaranteed for this action, but the aim is at least to add **reuse practices** to the set of circular strategies on show in the demo to make it as complete as possible and strengthen its character as an exemplary project.

Having reduced the embodied emissions, two more strategies remain in the circular toolbox: closing the loop through **design for deconstruction and reuse** and prolonging the service life of the building through **design for change**. These strategies have been explained in sections [4.7.1. Design for Deconstruction and Reuse](#) and [4.7.2. Design for Change](#)

6.10. Next steps

The next steps will be to define some final aspects in the design process. These are:

- The construction details, final Construction Budget and measurements
- Project execution and Building permit application
- Digitalization of the demo in BIM, in June 2024

6.10.1. Project Execution

By August 2024, we will reach the first major milestone (Mi4), with the **demo fully designed and digitised in BIM**, and production of the sandwich elements starting at Holland Composites in Lelystad. Seven months of **off-site fabrication** are scheduled between September 2024 and March 2025.

By March 2025, Holland Composites and VUB will also supply the 4 industrial samples of the **TRC floor elements** - as opposed to November 2025, as stated in the Grant Agreement. This way, the **on-site assembly** can start at Green Energy Park in April 2025, maintaining the deadline of May 2025, to **deliver the first phase of the demo** ('Belgian Prototype: demo').

The **second phase** will begin from then on, involving the **replacement of one of the storey floor elements** with the new TRC+AAC sandwich panel from T2.4⁵⁰ (HOL,VUB). This is scheduled for June 2026, leaving the summer months to do the necessary validation tasks and impacts assessments ('Demo: final'), marking at the same time the last Milestone (Mi8).

⁵⁰ Technical information on TRC sandwich panels developed in the project will be explained in the document: D2.3 Sandwich panel prototypes

7. Conclusion

7.1. Future ambitions

The construction, monitoring, modification, dismantling and reuse phases of the pilots will provide a practical process and documentation of the experience. These resources will be of great help to promote changes towards the circular economy in the construction sector, especially in the area of greatest influence of both pilots (the regions of influence of the cities of Barcelona and Brussels) but also in other entities and actors that are not necessarily in their ecosystems or located in their immediate surroundings.

Expected impact on the building sector: pilots or demonstrators of research and development projects on new materials, building systems, digital tools, methodologies and other resources offered to stakeholders generally aim to propose and accelerate changes in construction. These changes are not easy to achieve and require a certain time period to take place, but it is expected that the inputs from the Reconstruct pilots can be delivered quickly and effectively through the interaction, clustering and communication actions referred to in WP7.

Actors and entities with the greatest potential to benefit from the information: among them, those involved in precast concrete and mortar-based construction (Barcelona pilot) and prefabricated construction based on composite materials and lightweight systems (Brussels pilot). In particular, the focus is on stakeholders who have the capacity to influence decision-making processes on design, materials, construction techniques, resource management throughout the life cycle and reuse and recycling of building components. These stakeholders will be represented in the groupings referred to in Task 7.3 and its corresponding deliverable D7.3 but, in addition, many others that will not necessarily be contained in these relationship systems could take advantage of the information provided.

Potential stakeholder interaction activities: the WP7 task documentation details the main activities of presentation, discussion, validation and dissemination of information to be developed with the different stakeholders and entities identified. However, beyond these specific activities for the development of the Reconstruct project, others are already taking place and will take place in the future with other stakeholders that could multiply the scope of the information that the project will offer to the construction sector. Specifically, in relation to the pilots, these activities are the dissemination of the experience, the availability of technical documentation, on-site and virtual visits, the guidance that can be provided in similar actions in other projects and the collaboration with projects that are or will be considering similar pilot developments.

Information available after Reconstruct is completed: Some of the information will be available on its website, on social media, in conference publications and in specific repositories. This information, although it will no longer be updated due to the completion of the project, will be useful to the construction industry for a period of time estimated to be no less than 5 to 10 years. As part of the contents of the open access documents and tools, topics, forms and recommendations on how to continue, deepen and improve the research and development carried out in the project will be included. In this way, it is intended to promote a certain continuity, replicability and scalability based on the information provided on the pilots developed.

Use of information in teaching and research: some of the resources mentioned in the previous point will be particularly useful in the academic field, in the labour of universities, research centres and technology institutes. The use of information from the pilots' experience in teaching and research.

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

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